

Non-communicative Music Grammars of the 20th Century:

Origins, Mechanisms, and Consequences for Musical Communication

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Table of Contents

INNOVATION AND ART OF COMPOSITION	4
FASHION, MUSIC, AND MARKET COMPETITION BETWEEN FREELANCE COMPOSERS.....	6
THE IDEAL OF PERMANENT REVOLUTION IN ARTS	8
REACTIONARIES VS. INNOVATORS CHASING THE MIRAGE OF FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION	10
UNDER THE AEGIS OF “MANIFESTO”	11
WHEN “VISIONARIES” DECIDE FOR CONSUMERS - THE BIRTH OF HERMETIC GRAMMAR.....	12
REVOLUTION AGAINST REVOLUTIONARIES.....	15
NEW GRAMMARS AS A FORM OF BRANDING.....	17
THE PURPOSE OF NON-COMMUNICATION.....	18
NIHILISM AS A NEW STANDARD IN NEW MUSIC AND THE BACKLASH AGAINST IT.....	20
THE AVANT-GARDE HERITAGE IN THE 21 ST CENTURY.....	23
ARE MOST OF CONTEMPORARY COMPOSERS TECHNICALLY UNDERQUALIFIED?.....	28
WHEN “NON-COMMUNICATIVE” MUSIC IS MISINTERPRETED AS “COMMUNICATIVE”	32
THE PERFORMERS’ AND MUSICOLOGISTS’ CONUNDRUM: TO MAKE SENSE OF SENSELESS MUSIC OR NOT?.....	37

It is worth examining how the growing technicality of 20th-century music has led to the spread of a new type of music grammar – one that can be characterized as *non-communicative*. Such music is created by composers in a manner that is more of an invention rather than musical composition per se. The word “composition” used to imply an art of expression through sound, which has traditionally been related to communication of emotional information by means of conventional musical idioms of pitch, rhythm, meter, and harmony. However, this new type of music presents, instead, a coherent method of organizing the process of putting together some musical material. Its orientation towards facilitating *conception* rather than *perception* of music is what distinguishes this peculiar type of music, which can take quite different sonic shapes. What remains common between all of their varieties is:

- 1) their reliance on structures that are extremely difficult to perceive even for professional musicians who have gone through vigorous ear-training – and
- 2) a noticeable lack of functionality in their grammar to effectively convey emotional information.

This last point is not always obvious, since a performer can take liberty to invent a particular expression. There always existed some fuzzy area between what composers intended to express in their compositions and what performers actually found in their music. But this new strain of music that has become a norm for “art music” after the 2nd World War entirely delves into the murky waters of arbitrary interpretation. Composers of such music conceive it in a completely abstract scholastic way: they focus on aligning some structures, leaving the matter of expression entirely out – to be handled by performers and listeners, following the motto “let anyone figure out what my music is to them.” Supporters of such music usually see this approach as a merit – a sort of *freedom of imagination* that is called to answer *freedom of expression*. The cultural managers also often consider such riddling as positive, since it seems to widen the potential market for such music: after all, the listener is not required to be knowledgeable of any pre-existing music grammar, and is free to fantasize anything he wishes as the supposed “real meaning” of the auditioned work.

The problems with this approach are numerous. First of all, composing in this way discards the value of a musical composition. Why should the listener appreciate the patterns of sounds that the composer put together, if it is the listener who is supposed to invent the expression in music and enjoy it? What is the value that the composer has put in his music, if the listener can easily find

meaning in this way in any audible sounds? What is there for the listener to pay for? The common answer to this question is that subsidies from various cultural organizations cover most production costs for such music, creating an incentive for composers to continue producing it.

The second problem stems from the first: subsidization of this type of music effectively places those composers who would be willing to write music in an old traditional manner of expressing an “affect” at economic disadvantage. In a situation of ever-growing production costs, this constitutes a serious issue. The domain of “serious music” has been in notable decline for the past few decades: a handful of newly composed works survive their premiere, and those that manage to survive, do so because of the subsidies rather than public demand for this music. To this day, classical music remains the only music industry that makes profit from the music that was composed a century ago or earlier, and yet this industry persists producing something that no consumer really asks for.

The third problem is that many modern composers have limited experience in composing music that would be expressive in conveying emotional information that is of importance for the listener. Generations of composers who kept competing with each other in inventing more original grammar to bear the tag of their name gradually lost a know-how of writing good music and an intuition of good music, altogether. A significant majority of modern professionals would likely find it difficult to write a symphony, opera, or ballet capable of making a lasting impression on a wide audience. And the media, educational institutions, and concert agencies often provide ready-made explanations, such as attributing the disconnect to conservatism of taste among audiences.

The fourth problem threatens the very existence of the 4,000 years old tradition of Western classical music that so far has proved to be the most internationally renowned music system – composing non-communicative music may undermine the practice of composing communicative music. The very language of music has become compromised: the musical idioms that are meaningful and known to every competent musician and listener are “banned” from the vocabulary of modern composers as unoriginal and “outdated.” When language loses its functionality, it usually dies. It does not matter how perfect is the system of expression, if very few people use it. Latin language is often praised for its simplicity of grammar and great masterworks – but it ended up extinct, when new authors chose to express themselves in other languages. The cultural establishment of today also directs modern composers willing to express themselves in a meaningful way to head towards music domains other than classical music.

The accumulation of non-communicative grammars also complicates the field of musicology. Many scholars believe that it is their duty to study all existing types of music – especially the most recent ones. In order to be able to cross-examine music of older times as well as the newly composed music, they have to elaborate the old definitions and methods to the new music forms. The framework of study of communicative music becomes tweaked to include the non-communicative music. As the amount of new non-communicative grammars grows, the methodology of analysis of music form, theory of harmony, and other music disciplines become eroded with the notions set to reflect the organization of non-communicative music. Since the purpose of the latter is not to convey emotional content, analysis of its sound design should arguably be kept separate from the study of communicative music.

Therefore, it seems crucial at this point to define a set of guidelines for detection of non-communicative music and understanding of the underlying causes for its production. This is the goal of this paper.

Innovation and Art of Composition

Why would a composer choose to drop the “good old” way of expressing himself by means of musical idioms that everyone knows and therefore is capable of appreciating? Why to risk being not understood instead of following the way that proved to work? These questions seem rhetoric at the first glance. Nevertheless, they do have an answer, and the answer is – for the sake of *novelty*. Concern for novelty is the prime engine that drove the art of composition from the foundation of classical rhetoric to mimicry of scientific invention. This transition took a while and had a noble beginning.

Artistic innovation was appreciated in Western art from its origins, in Hellenic Greece. In the 5th century BC, Athens housed the rise of new style of music, associated with the theater, which featured originality of compositional thought and virtuosity of the performance.¹ Its first stars, such as Timotheus, were scorned by the supporters of the tradition, but celebrated by most of the population, setting precedence for seeking artistic superiority. Wide popularity of music contests played into the spread of appreciation for originality and competitive character of music profession. These traits suffered certain setback in Ancient Roman society, where challenging tasks, including composition and music performance, became the business of slaves. Further setback was served by the early Christian culture, which took position against the pagan music, on the whole, not to mention Christian advocacy for humility, which promoted anonymity in the arts and music.

The notions of originality and authorship came back in play during the Renaissance but applied mostly to extraordinarily talented masters and their works. The first time when being unique was regarded as a virtue in the public eye was turn of the 17th and 18th centuries in Western Europe. The development in politics, economics, society, culture, literature, and art, generated a new attitude toward life: rational, positive, and practical - contributing to the emergence of the concept of modernity. Secularization of intellectual thought, which accompanied the flourishing of capitalistic society, led to the pronounced changes in the perception of time: from the Christian *cyclic* concept to the New Age *linear* perception of time.

The notion of timeline incorporates the capacity of things to change. Therefore, processes that involved innovation became exposed in the eyes of the 18th century Europeans, leading to the rise of interest in the renewal of content in art works, including music. Music forms, generated in the mid 18th century, such as the sonata form, are characterized by the renovation of thematic material from exposition to recapitulation, and fixed structural changes in the unveiling of music form, so that at a given time, the listener can tell at which point in the musical movement he is.²

Modernity opened doors to innovation in Western music, which was previously rather conservative. More stylistic changes in history of music occurred in the 18th century than in the 17th century, and still more in the 19th century. As educated Europeans became “linear time conscious” through literature, theater, and music, they also became more susceptible to change. Their “ennui zone” shrank, and they felt the need for something new faster than did their parents, when listening to the same musical material. Throughout the 17th century, music sections overall become shorter, and the 18th century manifested growing popularity of miniature genres in instrumental and vocal music.

¹ Wallace, Robert W. “An Early Fifth-Century Athenian Revolution in Aulos Music.” *Harvard Studies in Classical Philology* 101 (September 2003): 73–92.

² Berger, Karol. *Bach’s Cycle, Mozart’s Arrow*. Los Angeles, CA: University of California Press, 2008, p.1-17.

Innovation became part of the musical life. Musical journals came into circulation with the chief purpose to keep the reader informed and abreast of the latest trends in music. Printed music made the spread of new compositional techniques much faster than ever before. As a result, the pace of renovation of musical lexicon kept accelerating. Although, all in all, things changed gradually. Music history contains examples of big leaps in innovation, for instance, by Monteverdi and Florentine Camerata, at the end of the 16th century. However, such leaps were still manifestations of evolution rather than revolution: the older grammars were not destroyed and at once substituted with new ones.

New forms have been in the process of development for decades, and those who propagated new forms were themselves masters of old forms, and often kept implementing older techniques concurrently with new ones. The development was gradual and somewhat “inclusive” rather than “exclusive”.

Innovation of the 19th century music defined three roads for the contemporary composer to develop his own style while complying with the canonic models of the past in order to reserve his place in the cultural “museum”. The three roads were, according to the excellent summary by Peter Burkholder:³

- 1) *Exoticism*: which attracted especially French and Russian composers, seeking to incorporate non-Western or “pseudo-non-Western” material in their compositions.
- 2) *Nationalism*: in an attempt to define their national identity in musical terms composers of every nation, in Europe and in Americas, explored Nationalism. They did so by reviewing all musical means and configuring them to highlight the character that was representative of a given nation.
- 3) *Folklorism*: this, set yet another direction away from the musical establishment towards a more trivial music representative of people rather than the nation. In Russia and other Eastern European countries this direction grew into an entire political movement.

The kind of “innovation” that became established in the 20th century, in general followed these three routes, but in a much more tempestuous way - it was much closer to being “revolutionary” rather than “evolutionary”. A big part of this was the rejection of the “museum”. “Innovators” wanted to exhibit their work into their own cultural space - following suit of the impressionist painters during the 1870s, who succeeded in splitting from the *Académie*, and establishing *Société Anonyme Coopérative des Artistes Peintres, Sculpteurs, Graveurs*.

This model of innovation involved denial of forms that were previously common, seen as the outdated past that contradicted modernity of the present. And the most principal difference from the past is that the 20th century innovations occur as a domino effect, on an ongoing basis, with a pace of just a few years separating a novelty from a previous “last thing”. Such mode of progress is more typical for commercial enterprises such as trend in clothing fashion, than it is for a natural development of means of communication. Not surprisingly novel music sacrificed quite a bit of intelligibility in sake of originality. And indeed, closer examination reveals that market competition is what stood behind the 20th century accelerated innovation.

³ Burkholder, J. Peter. “Museum Pieces: The Historicist Mainstream in Music of the Last Hundred Years.” *The Journal of Musicology* 2, no. 2 (April 1983): 115–34. <https://doi.org/10.2307/763802>.

Fashion, Music, and Market Competition between Freelance Composers

The idea of fashion – the range of variation in style that satisfies the need of a consumer for certain functionality as well as aesthetic sense – is probably as old as human culture, with the advent of figurative art and music probably occurring in the Aurignacian period in Western Europe.⁴ The first articles of clothing, headwear, footwear that are usually related to fashion concurred with invention of needle by a Cro-Magnon man.⁵ However, the typology of the costumes remained determined primarily by the climate and the lifestyle choice for quite a long time until the 14th century AD, undergoing little change within each civilization, once its clothing style was set, only differing between social classes.⁶

In the 14th century clothing acquired personal and national characteristics, became the interplay of social identity and personal taste, fueling demand in creativity of the dressmakers and frequent variations in style. Although each nation formed its own style of costume, Paris became the capital of the Empire of Fashion from the 15th century on.⁷ The fashion industry was brought to life by the growth of the middle class in most prosperous European states, and the desire of middle class families to imitate the styles of the upper classes and distinguish themselves from those below.⁸ The costume was hand-made by professionals out of the separately ordered accessories and were viewed as a reflection of the wearer's taste and prestige.

It is highly likely that the establishment of clothing fashion as a standard of sending a message of sophistication of taste and “good family” set the prototype of fashion for arts and music some time during the 17th century in France, England and the Netherlands.

The origin of fashion-hunger attitude can be traced to the 1910's times in Western Europe. There were some radical composers in the 19th century, such as Alkan, Smetana, and Mussorgsky, who disregarded the traditional music forms and harmony, and strove to develop their own idioms and formats of expression throughout their careers. However, their innovations did not catch up with their contemporaries, and did not lead to a substantial gain in their reputation as inventors during their lifetime. Radical innovations were not highly regarded by the 19th century society. Even moderate innovators, like Berlioz, Chopin, and Wagner (moderated by their respect for classic melodic idioms) had to overcome considerable resistance from the public, their peer composers, and performers, as it follows from their biographies. All in all, back then, it was more important to preserve the integrity of style than it was to be innovative. This kept the novel works within the idiomatic framework of comprehensibility for the conventional users.

⁴ Higham, Thomas, Laura Basell, Roger Jacobi, Rachel Wood, Christopher Bronk Ramsey, and Nicholas J. Conard. “Testing Models for the Beginnings of the Aurignacian and the Advent of Figurative Art and Music: The Radiocarbon Chronology of Geißenklösterle.” *Journal of Human Evolution* 62, no. 6 (June 2012): 664–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.03.003>.

⁵ Pendergast, Sara, Tom Pendergast, and Sarah Hermsen. *Fashion, Costume, and Culture: Clothing, Headwear, Body Decorations, and Footwear through the Ages*. Vol. 1. Farmington Hills, MI: The Gale Group, 2004, pp.6-7.

⁶ Boucher, François, and Yvonne Deslandres. *20,000 Years of Fashion: The History of Costume and Personal Adornment*. New York: H.N. Abrams, 1987, pp.12-13.

⁷ Challamel, Augustin, John Lillie, and Frances Cashel Hoey. *The History of Fashion in France, or, The Dress of Women from the Gallo-Roman Period to the Present Time*. New York: Scribner and Welford, 1882, p.61.

⁸ Kennedy, Alicia, Emily Banis Stoehrer, and Jay Calderin. *Fashion Design, Referenced: A Visual Guide to the History, Language, and Practice of Fashion*. Beverly, MA: Rockport Publishers, 2013, p.38.

The situation started changing after Wagner, Debussy, and Scriabin diversified the traditional grammar enough in every component, such as harmony, melody, rhythm, texture, and music form, and when the extremist groups such as Futurists and Dadaists, raised the threshold of what was considered socially unacceptable in relation to art. The significant boost in positivistic philosophy and science during the 19th century also contributed to forming the connotation between concepts of “invention” and “progress”. It became quite typical for composers, starting from Wagner on, to capitalize on the notion of progress in drawing “genealogies” of their respective style. By the 20th century this became common practice.⁹

As the idea of progress was becoming a referential framework in public opinion, the idea of innovation obtained a strongly positive charge. The beginning of the 20th century passed under an optimistic assumption for a bright future ahead and a strong faith in progress. Modernism was taking invention in a very straightforward way: the more the better - which led to enormous increase in innovation by composers. Younger generation was attracted to modernists celebrating innovation as a mark of vitality of their art.¹⁰

In the beginning of the 20th century the trend for innovation merged with an older trend for “progress”. The cultural consequence of technological progress during an intense industrialization of the 19th century Europe led to the increase in the importance of sciences and technology. Positivism of thought characterized most European cultures of the second half of the 19th century. Public perception of arts also became positivistically colored. The most obvious demonstration of this is the surge of literature on the techniques of musical performance. The collections of Etudes and treatises by these new “schools” differed from the earlier methods in their technicality of thought, systematic approach, and great methodic elaboration. The *First Principles of Pianoforte Playing* (1905) by Tobias Matthay is a good example of this thoroughly systematic “scientific” understanding of playing an instrument.

Positivistic thought determined the perception of history and culture during the 19th century. The pivotal impact came from Herbert Spencer with his adaptation of Darwin’s theory of evolution, to the field of culture, and specifically, the formulation of laws of progress and evolution in relation to music. From 1850s on, Spencerian laws found public recognition and prompted John Frederick Rowbotham to write the first “progressive” history of music. But it was Sir Hubert Parry, an Oxford scholar and composer, who challenged the biographical method which had dominated earlier music history research and proposed the model of tracing the evolution of musical forms as objective manifestations of spiritual activity. Thus, he became the most influential proponent of evolutionary historiography. Parry’s view on progression from monody to polyphony and then to harmony was accepted as the standard of Western musicology. However, it is useful to remember that this view regarded progress as a single model that is unilaterally true for all forms of music, therefore making it possible to determine, in absolute terms, the evolutionary line, from savagery to civilization, as to on which point a given music form rests. This model also allowed for projections into future.¹¹

⁹ Perry, Jeffrey (2000) - Music, Evolution and the Ladder of Progress. Music Theory Online, Volume 6, Number 5, November 2000.

¹⁰ Taruskin, Richard (2009) - Music in the Early Twentieth Century: The Oxford History of Western Music, Oxford University Press, New York, p. 1-2.

¹¹ Allen, Warren Dwight (1962) - Philosophies of Music History: A Study of General Histories of Music, 1600-1960. Dover Publications, New York p.104-117.

And this is exactly what attracted the ultra-modernistic composers. Stravinsky and Schoenberg's rhetoric was built exactly on linking the technical features that characterized their music, to the evolutionary process of the past - in an attempt to legitimize and validate their respective modernizations. Such strategy proved to be effective and made an impression on numerous critics and musicologists, as well as performers and peer composers, initiating discourse about the future of music language and the direction of its development - all of which was built on the premise of "self-propelled" evolution of music structures. The chief import from such philosophy was the notion of wrongness of the "common sense": what appears as a norm today will become obsolete in time and give way to what is "correct" in the future. This is as though science proves "common sense" to be fundamentally wrong, and as though the composer-innovator is not making things up, but just "adjusts" for the evolutionary momentum ahead of time and becomes the driving force in letting the history fulfill itself.

The Ideal of Permanent Revolution in Arts

Eventually, the evolutionary projection strategy succeeded in convincing the public in that something that does not appear to make sense now, may be regarded as useful and progressive in the future. That is how the ultra-modernistic art became justified: by rubbing in the point that the inability to see the value of the "evolutionary innovation" is a sign of lack of expertise throughout the course of evolution. Hence, arguing against artistic innovations was testimony to ignorance and historic shortsightedness. This overturn of consensus was set in place somewhat by the 1920s. Not much has changed since - the belief in "progress" may be out, but the word "progressive" is still understood as a viable and positive term. In today's world, the opposite of "progressive" - "conservative" - has also retained its negative connotation in relation to art, as Richard Taruskin puts it: the central myth in musicology of today is still to "marry the Permanent Revolution to the Great Tradition".¹²

Such "marriage" has attracted many composers of the avant-garde lineage as well, from Arnold Schoenberg to Tristan Murail. The paradoxical combination of revolutionary attitude and the evolutionary claims seems to peacefully coexist in the mind of the avant-garde artist without realizing the inherent contradiction in such combination. An artist needs to justify his revolutionary mission by the evolutionary development of the music structures - as though these structures have life of their own, and that he is just allowing them to "eagerly" come into being just as they are. Hence, the flavor of "scientific" objectivity combined with revolutionary phraseology. The desperate need to be original by all costs is still at the heart of this perplexed artistic position. The need in historic lineage is secondary, supportive of this quest for originality that defines the very notion of avant-garde art in general.¹³

The greatest myth of the avant-garde movement is the story of Stravinsky's *The Rite of Spring*, conceived in an attempt to revolutionize music language and to fulfill this goal by establishing a new type of discourse. *The Rite of Spring* became instantly famous in 1913 for the scandal it produced at its premiere and the abnormal degree of innovation it injected in a single work, as compared to

¹² Taruskin, Richard (2009) - *The Danger of Music and Other Anti-Utopian Essays*. University of California Press, Los Angeles, California, p. 364.

¹³ Krauss, Rosalind (1986) - *The Originality of the Avant-Garde and Other Modernist Myths*, MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass., p.157.

everything that was publicly performed before it. This was not the introduction of a new idiom, a new subject, or even a new topic - it was offering of a new language - the language that was not conceived completely from scratch (it utilized elements that were previously known), but nevertheless it was new in its grammar and many "invented" elements.

The work was "experimental" in a direct sense: it was a trial and error on the part of Stravinsky to put forth such an opus. The work went far beyond the point of lapse of evolution - how natural languages usually progress - and stepped into the area of revolution, a forceful takeover by an inventor pushing for his invention. The pendulum of history swung one way during the premiere, devastating Stravinsky, but promptly went the other direction at the next performance, just a year later, this time in a concert hall, conducted by Pierre Monteaux, scoring a significant success.

Stravinsky played it remarkably well and, on top of everything else, certainly got lucky. Marketing was a big part of his win. First of all, Diaghilev, the genius producer, did everything to ignite the scandal at the premiere. Secondly, Stravinsky calculated well and was timely to switch from the medium of ballet - where he was subordinate to the choreographer - to the concert program music, where he was the sole winner. In this transition Stravinsky spouted his genealogical theories, and retroactively invented the conceptual meaning for his work, and exaggerated the degree of its originality (he claimed to have only one folk quotation, whereas in fact there were nine).¹⁴

Somehow things fell right in place for him, and his music generated enormous resonance. His work indeed laid the foundation for a new language of expression adopted by hundreds of composers. This language turned out to be quite effective in communication and therefore has stayed functional over time: idioms of *The Rite of Spring* are still in use in the practice of music making, and compositions written in such manner are still performed worldwide. It would not be a big stretch to say that 20th century Western musical culture was created in the image of Stravinsky.¹⁵

But the spread of Stravinskian idioms was not the only historic outcome from the success of *The Rite of Spring*. This ballet proved to be pivotal in generating a new social trend in the profession of the composer - something that Taruskin wittily called "rush-to-the-patent-office modernism". Inspired by Stravinsky's triumph, composers started following his path, trying hard to invent something new, something that could be presented as though it emancipates creativity, something shocking enough to generate scandal - and then support their music with some kind of theory that would make it look important to the contemporaries.¹⁶

Henry Cowell became credited as the father of cluster music to be performed on the piano with fists, forearms, and palms. Julián Carrillo came up with the world's first microtonal composition in quarter-, eighth- and sixteenth-tones for unconventional instruments and specially trained voices. Edgar Varese invented music without musical sounds, limiting the entire composition to percussive instruments and sirens. Arseny Avraamov went even further and scored a symphony for guns, factory whistles, ship foghorns, and airplanes. George Antheil had to think really hard to come up with something new and had his moment of eureka in writing a ballet where all music was played as loud as possible.

¹⁴ Taruskin, Richard (2009) - *The Danger of Music and Other Anti-Utopian Essays*. University of California Press, Los Angeles, California, p. 421-422.

¹⁵ *ibid* p. 420.

¹⁶ Taruskin, Richard (2009) - *Music in the Early Twentieth Century: The Oxford History of Western Music*, Oxford University Press, New York, p. 193-195.

“Innovation” became a requisite for new compositions, no matter what the invention – and turned into the principle source of aesthetic validation of new music. And the situation has not really changed. In the 21st century Einojuhani Rautavaara is still earning points by producing music with “bilateral keyboard symmetry” (with innovative graphic notation) for a symmetrical year of 2002.¹⁷

Reactionaries vs. Innovators Chasing the Mirage of Freedom of Expression

Western composers, such as Rachmaninov, Medtner, and R. Strauss, who kept writing in traditional tonal idioms were stigmatized by Western critics as retrograde. Thus, one of Rachmaninov’s best works, “Symphonic Dances”, was pinned by the New York critics for sounding “long and derivative,” and as being “a rehash of old tricks”. Rhapsody on a Theme of Paganini was “not philosophical, significant, or even artistic”, “it’s something for the audiences”. Much of criticism had to do not with the work per se, but with its tonal base, viewed as having nothing more to say in a world where art had demonstrably “progressed”, and originality and innovation had come to mean everything.¹⁸

Worse, still, was the situation for those composers who had not established a big name before the 1930s. Negative connotations of tonal music in conservatories and in the media were one of prime motives for creation of famous 20th century hoaxes by talented musicians: Henri and Marius Casadesus, and Mikhail Goldstein.

Nothing was hit as hard in compositional practices of the 20th century as metric organization. Just as the composers of the first half of the century were concerned about the motoric effect of their music, composers after the 2nd World War allied to fight meter with rhythm. The conviction that traditional metric organization is primitive and rigid, and that for some reason it has been neglected by previous composers, and therefore needs modernization.

Throughout the 19th century composers progressively developed the dichotomy of rhythmic content versus metric form. Romantic composers like Schumann, Chopin, and Brahms made use of metric dissonance, where the rhythmic figures accumulated their violation of the metric pulse, followed by metric resolution, when the phrases coincided with the meter.

The genesis of atonal music brought in further expansion of rhythmic factor, proving the ontological connection between tonality and meter. In general, all forms of atonal music are characterized by weak metric periodicity. The transition from tonality to atonality corresponds with a number of composers abandoning the bar-line in their compositions: Eric Satie, Arthur Lourié, Olivier Messiaen. Even when atonal compositions maintain a regular time signature, often the metric pulse is purely nominal, and hardly evident through audition of the music.

Starting from Webern, avant-garde composers strove for complete segregation from meter, making sure that the rhythmic content was completely free from any trace of metric structure. In order to secure complete unrepeatedness of the rhythmic content, a number of composers during the 1950s

¹⁷ Paul, Brandon (2008) - Bilateral Keyboard Symmetry in the Music of Einojuhani Rautavaara. The Ohio State Online Music Journal, Volume 1, Number 2.

¹⁸ Franklin, Peter (2000) - Modernism, Deception, and Musical Others: Los Angeles circa 1940. In: Western Music and its Others, ed. G. Born & D. Hesmondhalgh, University of California Press, Berkeley, p. 143-162.

came up with systems of serialization of rhythm, explicitly stating that metric divisions are retained in their scores purely for the convenience of synchronization of parts.

Stockhausen, Boulez, and Nono were unhappy with even the hardly traceable periodicity that was left in their serial opuses due to the integer values of twelve - usually rhythmic periods of 78, comprised of the sum of all rhythmic values from 1 to 12. These composers found such periodicity to resemble a 6/8 pulse and, therefore, went out of their way excoriating the "evil" 78 periods by means of extra rhythmic rows or subdivision of rhythm into "phases" or "formants" - as in Stockhausen's music.¹⁹

Under the Aegis of "Manifesto"

One of the most influential examples of such "timing reform" that has served as a model for the more recent compositional techniques was introduced by Karlheinz Stockhausen. Like many other post-modernistic composers, almost right from the start of his career, Stockhausen denounced all traditional idioms that existed before the 1920s, including not only classical, but all other so-called "natural" forms of music (folk, popular, etc.). Instead, he strove to generate his own rules for putting sounds together. Following the steps of Schoenberg, he started off by inventing a novel concept.

In 1957, he comes up with the observation that pitch and duration can be considered as manifestation of the same phenomenon on a microtonal level - since the period in rhythm can be equal to the period in frequency (at about 1/16 sec). A sound-event is heard as a pitch if it occurs at a rate faster than 16 cycles per second but turns into duration at a slower rate. From that, Stockhausen formed the idea of matching the pitch and duration in tones to build a composition.²⁰

His presentation makes a hasty and unclear impression: goals are not stated at the beginning of the discussion, argument point is constantly shifting, discourse is overly long. The standard acoustic terminology is mixed up in both, original German and English translation: the term "phase" is used instead of "period", "formant" instead of "harmonic", and "filed" instead of "band". Peculiarly enough, Stockhausen did not correct his terminology in the second edition, but placed a statement acknowledging his lack of adherence to what was standard. This is yet another demonstration of his disinterest in communication with the end user of his creation.

The point of presentation is by no means new: Ezra Pound and Henry Cowell discussed it about 30 years earlier. However, what is new in Stockhausen's text is the idea of correcting the musical notation for inequality of representation of time and pitch. He seeks a method of organization where tones would be notated by reflection of the increments of the 12-element scales, simultaneously in pitch and duration. Most of the article is dedicated to the problems in such a notation, occasionally skipping to the discussion of variability of timing in performance practice.²¹

The idea of organic unity of time and pitch falls on the ground of some highly speculative philosophical theory by Viktor von Weizsäcker (1886-1957), a physiologist who employed the

¹⁹ Schnittke, Alfred (2004) - The Works on Music [Statyi o Muzyke], ed. Ivashkin A., Kompozitor, Moscow, p. 70-71

²⁰ Stockhausen K. (1957) - «...how time passes...», Die Reihe, 1957, No.3. p. 10-50.

²¹ Roads, Curtis (2004) - Microsound. The MIT Press, p. 72-74.

Gestalt psychology in an attempt to theoretically define the unit of perception. The part of Weizsäcker's theory dealt with the presentation of biological events not as fixed responses to environmental stimuli, but as a result of previous experience that, for some reason, was constantly repatterned. This theory must have attracted Stockhausen's attention (as he himself later admitted). Stockhausen's import from Weizsäcker was the motto "time is in things, and things are not in time" - interpreted as such that each living object has its own time - with projection on music structures, holding that each sound calls for its own time. "Uniform time is only an abstract thing which can exist for traffic, trains, and airplanes", but not in music. "time becomes completely relative, depending on the material used", and "breaking through the routine of time" would make "things reveal their mystery".²²

With such ideas in mind, and with his "invention" at hand, Stockhausen heads back into the historic past (likely, following Schoenberg's path). But Schoenberg was sensitive to the semiotics of the old grammar and never really pushed for his dodecaphonic principles to be applied to old music - for instance, regarding the last fugue from *The Well-Tempered Klavier* as a mere indication of Bach's interest to 12 tones as a particular entity.

Unlike Schoenberg, Stockhausen retroactively pushed his own idea all the way: claiming that Mozart applied the numeric proportion of the tonic-dominant (3:2) and tonic-subdominant (2:3) progressions to the metric and rhythmic organization in his cadences, creating combinations of two and three bar groups, as well as four bar phrases alternating with 6 bar phrases. Stockhausen claimed that the same principle governs the changes of dotted rhythms by straight division, and the switches from regular division to triplets. He coined the concepts of "metric cadence" and "rhythmic cadence", and declared them equivalents of the harmonic cadence, generalizing from this a metric syncopation law, according to which rhythmic and metric irregularity versus regularity are the same as dissonance versus consonance in music grammar. According to him, regular-irregular succession is the beginning of the cadence, whereas irregular-regular succession is the conclusion of the cadence.²³

With the historic authority in his pocket, Stockhausen felt comfortable to advance to making a general claim of "unified time" which embodies the main perceptual categories of color, harmony, melody, meter, rhythm, dynamics, and form. Again, much of Stockhausen's attention went into the technicalities of division of such time in order to gather all the properties of sound under a single umbrella. In a pivotal article "The concept of unity in electronic music" all of his discourse goes into technical matters, and there is not even a single statement about how such "unified time" is helpful for the listener to receive the message in music.²⁴

When "Visionaries" Decide for Consumers - The Birth of Hermetic Grammar

In fact, Stockhausen was completely disinterested in communication with the audience, apparently without envisaging an "ideal listener" during his creative process. Moreover, the very issue of perceptibility of his innovative structures is off the table in his considerations for composition.

²² Paul, David (1997) - Karlheinz Stockhausen. *Seconds Magazine*, No.44 p. 64-73.

²³ Stockhausen K. (1961) - *Kadenzrhythmik der Mozart*. Darmstädter Beiträge zur neuen Musik. Darmstadt, 1961, band 4, p. 38-72.

²⁴ Stockhausen K., Barkin, E. (1962) - The concept of unity in electronic music, *Perspectives of new music*, Autumn, 1962, v.1 No.1., p. 39-48.

Paradoxically, as an adherent of the physiological theorist, Weizsäcker, Stockhausen is explicit in his statements that perception does not need any consideration, since it is infinitely “adjustable”. He disregards the universal notions, such as “just noticeable difference” in pitch intervals. He holds that there are no absolute limits, and one is always able to raise one's perceptual limits through exercise.

Stockhausen was aware of his disagreement with cognitive sciences but dismissed the scientific data. Thus, he stated that he used pitch intervals smaller than the Pythagorean comma - which is normally not considered to be perceivable - but that he has found it to be quite perceivable - “you can certainly perceive it”.²⁵

Stockhausen sees the purpose of new music not to follow perception, but to change it, to help people “enlarge their consciousness”. He seems to sincerely believe that “inventing” new forms of organization somehow will influence the listener, perhaps in the manner of music therapy. This attitude must be responsible for him ignoring matters of communication altogether and zooming into the technicalities of structuring: developing special scales of “points”, “groups”, “moments” for sound parameters and methods for aligning them (“formulas”) into “process-plan” pieces (like “Plus-Minus”).

Resolving the problems of whether to crystallize parameters into elements, or to crystallize elements into formula - all of which become a sort of a ritual for him, akin to an alchemist proceeding to prepare raw material out of which to create a special potion. The satisfaction from inferring the formula that is a mini-composition of all possible musical aspects, “reflecting the image of galaxy”, with nuclear tones and accessories surrounding them like stars and planets - must be the end goal of the entire process of Stockhausen’s composition, completely devoid of any substance - whether or not such attitude is indeed expressed and perceived by the listener.²⁶

Taking rhythm matrices, reordering them by number matrices, then combining them together to form separate columns of a “Final Rhythm Matrix” consisting of six columns and six rows, afterwards choosing 19 of the 36 blocks, and finally deriving the pitch content out of the initial rhythm - all of this procedure bears a resemblance to an alchemical pursuit -- intricate in method but uncertain in communicative outcome.²⁷

1. Example: Stockhausen - *Klavierstück XI*, Rhythm Matrix 1.²⁸

²⁵ Cott, Jonathan (1974) - Stockhausen: Conversations with the Composer. London: Pan Books, p. 89.

²⁶ Coenen, Alcedo (1994) - Stockhausen's paradigm: A survey of his theories. *Perspectives of new music*, 32(2) p. 200-225.

²⁷ Truelove, Stephen (1998) - The Translation of Rhythm into Pitch in Stockhausen's *Klavierstück XI*. *Perspectives of New Music*, Vol. 36, No. 1 (Winter, 1998), pp. 189-220.

²⁸ Ibid.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							

2. Example: *Klavierstück XI*. Number Matrix 1:

6	1	4	3	7	5	2
1	3	6	5	2	7	4
4	6	2	1	5	3	7
3	5	1	7	4	2	6
7	2	5	4	1	6	3
5	7	3	2	6	4	1

3. Example: Conversion of matrix data into the notation of the score (fragment):

However, even if the composer is convinced by such organizing principles, this does not necessarily make the resulting music communicative. The creative output of Stockhausen is built around an

abstract idea that is taken a priori and is strictly reinforced by the material of musical tones without any justifications or considerations for the listeners. The primary purpose of the composition here appears to be not conveying information to the listeners, but the intellectual satisfaction of the composer -- akin to accomplishing a challenging mental puzzle. The satisfaction from having the entire piece as “the one time-spectrum of a single fundamental duration” - a genuine (according to Stockhausen) “tonality” - is an experience private to the composer, not necessarily shared by listeners or performers.²⁹

The listener or the performer can believe that they are realizing some concept through Stockhausen’s music, but the makeup of this music is such that no meaning can really be conveyed through it. Non-communicative techniques are all similar in setting a “make-belief” condition for the consumption of such music, which often produces a religious connotation. There are numerous works composed in non-communicative techniques with religious or mystic titles suggesting some kind of a bliss – such as Stockhausen’s *Mantra* (1970). In fact, a title like that in combination with the chaotically complex sound, and a conceptual meaning verbalized by the composer to accompany the publication of his score, and/or with a huge emphasis on the organization of the technique in the piece – are all pointers that this music belongs to the category of “non-communicative”.

Revolution Against Revolutionaries

Serial technique is not the only one that can be systemically incomprehensible. For instance, John Cage’s music has a completely different sound and organization from Stockhausen’s, yet it is as “non-communicative” by its design. Cage is a lot more open about it though than is Stockhausen. In his description of his process of composition Cage claims that following his method established the *I-Ching*, which according to him consists of throwing three coins to decide every aspect of his music structure. He goes at length to explain which combinations of the sides of the coins result in which hexagrams, and how to derive values from them for each aspect of the performance, diligently scattering the instruction with Chinese terms. At the end, he states that this is the way to make a musical composition, the “continuity of which is free of individual taste and memory” and also of the “traditions of the art”. The sounds “center within themselves”, “unimpeded by service to any abstraction”. This composition is not to be judged. It is absolutely perfect: “a mistake is beside the point”, because anything that happens during the performance is justified by the composer.³⁰

4. Example: John Cage – *Music of changes*.

²⁹ Cott, Jonathan (1974) - Stockhausen: Conversations with the Composer. London: Pan Books, p. 76.

³⁰ Cage, John (1961) - Silence: Lectures and Writings, Wesleyan University Press, Hanover NH p. 57-59.

We can observe here patterns similar to Stockhausen's method of "time unity". In the same way Cage arbitrarily decides to pick an abstract principle and systematically apply it to the organization of music tones in place of traditional means of organization. Cage completely cuts off with the history of music before him, following De Kooning's motto "The past does not influence me; I influence it." Cage thinks that neither any study of the past music nor performance is necessary. For him the history of music starts with "experimental music" and is bound to originality and inventiveness.³¹

Because of his nihilistic orientation, Cage is not seeking any historic roots for his technique in classical music. Instead of music history he goes to the history of religion, using scraps of information that have "holy" status: from *I-Ching* ("Book of Changes", a mythological cosmogonic document of about 20th century B.C.) to anecdotes about Chan Buddhist monks (Middle Ages China). What matters to Cage is that such religious systems are exotic to the Western audience, hard to grasp and - as in the case with Buddhism - disregards reality as it appears to be "false". This opens Cage's hands to experiment with absurd methods of musical organization - as though in doing so he calls our attention to the "falsehood" of our values. In fact, after reading the main monuments of Chinese ancient philosophy of Buddhist orientation, it will become clear that: a) adherents of these teachings in fact practiced traditional music and fine art according to the conventional norms; b) their realization of "falsehood" of the sensible world did not lead them to ridicule it; c) they did not make any profit from preaching their beliefs, and conducted a monastic life style.

Cage's Buddhist insights into compositional organization have little to do with the content of Tripitaka, Abhidharma, and sutras; his ideas only follow some superficial similarity with the anecdotes about the Buddhist masters. The specialists in Cage's music have not been able to demonstrate any evidence of structural or procedural affinities between Cage's compositions and Asian traditional music and/or philosophy. So far, research only established ample cases of Cage borrowing ideas for his Asian rhetoric from his social contacts, like Lou Harrison and Richard Lippold.³²

Cage's reputation of a musical philosopher who specialized in demonstrating relativity of concepts by means of musical sounds seems to be more of a public image he carefully constructed throughout his life, rather than a real thing. High integrity of ethics and metaphysics - very typical for any Asian philosophy - has little to do with Cage's life. Whenever asked directly about his Buddhist connections, Cage always admitted that he was neither practicing Buddhism, nor Hinduism, despite his enthusiasm for teachings of D.T. Suzuki and Ananda Coomaraswamy.³³

More than anything Cage seemed to have been concerned with *épatage* behavior - driven by the desire to shock the Westerners with his disrespect to the authorities held by majority in high esteem, and instead exhibit reverence for figures that most people did not know anything about or for whom they had little regard. Earlier in his life, Cage was more open in disclosing this attitude - not

³¹ *ibid* p. 67-75.

³² Patterson, David W. (2002) - Cage and Asia: History and sources. In: *The Cambridge companion to John Cage*. Cambridge, p. 41-59

³³ Clarkson, Austin (2001) - The intent of the musical moment: Cage and the transpersonal. In: *Writings through John Cage's music, poetry, and art*. David Bernstein and Christopher Hatch (eds) University of Chicago Press, p. 62-112.

camouflaging himself as an Eastern guru. Thus, during his teaching career in Black Mountain College in Asheville, North Carolina, in 1948, Cage's lecture provoked an uproar when he praised Eric Satie as the model for composers – for his “brevity and unpretentiousness” – as opposed to “lengthiness and impressiveness”³⁴ of those composers who chose to follow Beethoven who was accused by Cage in shipwrecking “the art on an island of decadence.” Cage's lecture reportedly prompted students to burn Beethoven's recordings and sheet music.

Later in his life, Cage learned how to put on a more respectable image by playing on the relative novelty of the Eastern philosophy to the Western public. Ideas of popularizers of Zen and Hindu religions provided a philosophical framework for what was otherwise a deliberately content-free approach to composition – lending an air of profundity to his compositional method. And here he did not stop short of even plagiarizing Mao, as David Patterson³⁵ recently established: apparently, many of Cage's texts contain direct quotes from Wheelwright and McFarlane's “*The Chinese Road to Socialism: Economics of the Cultural Revolution*”³⁶ in relation to Mao - without giving any credit to the authors. What kind of sincere and coherent philosophy can combine Buddhism, Hinduism, and Maoism?

New Grammars as a form of Branding

In reality, Cage's Buddhism, like Stockhausen's “absolute time”, are just forms of marketing - more specifically, branding. For them, the main purpose of these techniques is to mark their compositions as distinct from those of other composers. The rest of it is fiction that can vary from one non-communicative technique to another.

The function of a “normal” traditional technique is to facilitate communication of information. This function is responsible for shaping technique. When the type of information to be transmitted changes, the technique becomes transformed and eventually can be replaced altogether by some new technique - as it happened with the general bass replacing strict polyphony. Schoenberg's dodecaphony also falls within this naturally driven, functional techniques, since its rules have been gradually defined from the practice of conveying an antagonist conflicting content via music structures.

Cage's “technique” is devoid of any informative content by its design. And Cage did not make any secret of his emptiness of musical ideas. In his interviews he explicitly stated: “*I don't hear music in my head. I only hear music when it's audible.... [Many composers] write down what they hear... Nothing is playing in my head.*”³⁷ And when the interviewer asked whether Cage wrote music “*in order to hear it*” and please himself with surprise, Cage clearly confirmed.³⁸

³⁴ Silverman, Kenneth (2010) - *Begin Again: A Biography of John Cage*, Alfred A. Knopf, New York, p. 134-135.

³⁵ Patterson, David W. (2012) - "Political" or "Social"? : John Cage and the remolding of Mao Tse-Tung . In: *Cage & Consequences*. Edited by Julia H. Schröder and Volker Straebel. Hofheim: Wolke, 2012, p.51-65.

³⁶ Wheelwright E.L. & McFarlane B. (1971) - *The Chinese Road to Socialism: Economics of the Cultural Revolution*, New York: Monthly Review Press.

³⁷ Cage, John (in conversation with Joan Retallack). *Musicage: Cage Muses on Words, Art, Music*. Wesleyan University Press, 1996, p. 86.

³⁸ *Ibid.* p. 124.

Notably, Arnold Schoenberg himself summarized his impression of Cage's achievements in taking lessons in composition from him as: "Inventor! An inventor of genius. *Not a composer, no, not a composer, but an inventor.*"³⁹ A composer who does not imagine music internally and does not design its expressive organization occupies, arguably, a different creative role. But then the compositional technique advocated by such a person should not be regarded as "composition" either – "invention", perhaps, but not composition.

However, contrary to common sense, the approach toward making music by Cage and Stockhausen became two highways for the development of modern music. The strict serial approach elaborated by Stockhausen, Boulez, and Nono within the Darmstadt school turned into the official status quo of post-tonal composition as a new "classic". And Cage's aleatoric approach exemplified the alternative option, not as prestigious as dodecaphony, but overall acceptable, nonetheless.

The serial technique canonized at Darmstadt has been the one that has determined the entire philosophy of new music up until today. Non-serial music, occasionally performed and even produced at Darmstadt, has not had any impact on the serial orientation which remained at the forefront of Darmstadt's reputation as the avant-garde leading force in the world, holding serialism as the highest achievement of the European avant-garde.

The message from Darmstadt was that of rebellion against the traditional norm, aesthetic control, and political power - no matter what. And this was despite any stylistic modification that took place at times of triumvirate by Nono, Boulez, and Stockhausen (1956-1961) - Boulez' directorship (1962-65), and Stockhausen's domination (1966-1974) or after his leave. The phenotype of technique and its treatment of modern avant-garde was set in the 1950s.⁴⁰

Post-modernistic techniques, be it Cage's or Stockhausen's, differ from older techniques, including modernistic (of the 1920-40s), by being anti-communicative. Schoenberg designed his works so that the musical structures in the composition would follow a certain dramatic plot in presenting a particular character, image, mood, or attitude. But this is exactly what many post-war composers did not want to do – as noticed by their own colleagues.

The purpose of non-communication

Thus, Luciano Berio complains that the image of a cosmopolitan composer, busy with conveyer-production of complex constructs, becomes a commonplace. Never before was a composer as close to becoming an alien figure within a society he lives in as has been the case since the advent of post modernistic techniques. Berio blames it on the composer's practice of designing new perceptual methods for the listener. Modern composers tend to zoom into technical manipulations of tones forgetting that these tones are "symbols of reality". Such composers can provide exhaustive

³⁹ Letter from Peter Yates to Cage, 8 August 1953, John Cage Correspondence, C7 (1950– 1959), Deering Music Library, Northwestern University.

⁴⁰ Attinello, Paul (2007) - Postmodern or Modern: A Different Approach to Darmstadt. *Contemporary Music Review*, Vol. 26 No.1, p. 25 – 37.

descriptive analysis of their creations yet are helpless in grasping the meaning of the music they create. This makes theories of their technique useless for the creation of music.⁴¹

Witold Lutoslawski complains about the absence of any fabula in majority of works starting from the 1960s. Instead, composers montage pre-conceived structures. They do not imagine how their work unveils itself in sound and, as a result, lose the purport of their work – not seeing the forest behind the trees in their music structures. Modern music, as a rule, does not consider the issue of perception. Not everything fixable in the score is perceptible. None of the great composers of the past ignored the matter of perception. They played their music while composing and adjusted the structures according to their perception. They lived through their music. It was unthinkable for them to compose by stitching some abstract fragments together on paper. No wonder why works generated by such stitching sound static, boring, and leave the listener untouched – if not disturbed.⁴²

It is important to point out that even highly disciplined techniques, such as serialism, do not totally defy the possibility of writing expressive music. Most works of Alban Berg are recognized as a landmark of heightened emotionality. Even such technique as “total serialism” that completely discards conventional means of expression has produced several notable works of undeniable expressive merit - such as *Il Canto Sospeso* (1956) by Luigi Nono. So, the term “non-communicative” refers not only to the choice of compositional technique, but also to the implementation of that technique by a particular composer.

Although the choice of coding structures is the primary source of problem in communication here. Thus, adhering to serial rules stiffens the melodic phrases, stripping them off of their tonal proportionality, while knocking out their harmonic pulse of tension-resolution waves. Serialization of rhythm leaves even less space for deliberate communication of character in music. In order to implement a simple rhythmic acceleration for expressive purposes, the composer has to tweak the rows and their permutations – and it takes the calculator to appreciate his efforts.

A number of post-modernistic composers had backgrounds in mathematics and engineering (Boulez, Xenakis, Denisov). Seeking to build a “perfect” structure, instead of relying on pre-existing idioms of melody, rhythm, and harmony, they pursued formal adherence to an abstract numerical principle with their serial approach – “believing” in some harmonizing effect from perfect coherence of numbers. It is quite typical for composers of non-communicative works to see their goal in maintaining proportionality, rather than to observe rhetoric concerns of convincing the listener in authenticity of a particular image, affect or happening, conveyed by music.

One seeming advantage of this approach is the simplicity of estimation of a non-communicative work: no need to worry about recognizing idioms and interpretation of their rendition. The evaluation of such work is rather straightforward and objective: all it takes is knowing a set of rules adopted by the composer and tracing the adherence to such rules throughout the score. This is sufficient to validate the work and regard its magnitude in relation to some other works. The only extra factor here to weigh is the novelty of the technical decision that went into the work.

⁴¹ Berio, Luciano (1968) - The composer on his work: meditation on a twelve-tone horse, *Christian Science Monitor*, 15 July 1968, p. 8.

⁴² Nikolskaya I. (1988) - Witold Lutoslawski on himself, on his works and on traditions; Interview XX [W.L. o sebe, o tvorcestve, o traditsiyah. Intervyu XX] *Soviet Music Magazine*, 1988 No.9 p. 103-112.

When the communicative function in music is abandoned, and when the composer does not optimize his music to speak to the listener, the structures of his work tend to become governed by the marketing laws.

The composer intuitively starts looking for a pattern of organization that would make him become noticed - not necessarily through audition, but through various concomitant factors: title of the piece, the instruments incorporated, its artistic manifesto, etc. He keeps adjusting his product line until by trial he finds out which image works best for generating critical interest. He then starts raising brand awareness of his product. If the brand recall falls, he reconfigures the brand elements and launches an update - a new development in his technique. The careers of Cage and Stockhausen very comfortably fit this model of branding.

Hans Werner Henze writes how oppressive the Darmstadt School was in relation to young composers who employed any traditional structures in their music. Boulez and Stockhausen did not tolerate anything but the iconic post-Webernian avant-garde, ignoring the booing audiences at night concerts. Henze picks on the non-communicative character of music propagated at Darmstadt, and attributes it to the fashion in the upper-class society of that day. He also notices the religious mystic flavor of the model works appreciated at the school, and the aversion to the very idea of "simple, concrete, and comprehensible communication" between music and the listeners.⁴³

Nihilism as a new Standard in New Music and the Backlash against it

The formalistic and self-promoting flavor of non-communicative compositions apparently did not pass unnoticed even by the avid supporters of avant-garde. Luigi Nono created havoc in 1959 with his lecture "Historical Presence in Music Today". Nono accused his colleagues of hiding from real life with all its social and cultural issues, into an ivory tower of future-oriented abstraction. Indeed, composers of the modernistic generation, such as Prokofiev and Stravinsky, measured their works against the works of composers of the past while crafting their compositions, and afterwards they evaluated the success of their works against the success of their predecessors. Post-modernistic composers found a more convenient way – by just dismissing any successful predecessors as "anachronist".

Target of Nono's attack was John Cage, whose chance-oriented compositional methods had earlier created a sensation at Darmstadt and influenced Stockhausen and Boulez. Nono labeled chance taking as "morally flawed", Cage's idea of "freeing of sounds" as "spiritual suicide", and concentration on technicalities as betrayal of the composer's duty to influence the society. Nono warned his fellow composers of the dangers of succumbing to an ultimately nihilistic temptation in their blind rejection of the critical role of history.

Here Nono was defending Schoenberg's legacy, bound to it by his aesthetic and ethical values, as well as personal attachment (his first opus, that decided his compositional career, was variations on a Schoenberg's theme. Also, Nono was married to Schoenberg's daughter, Nuria). "Sounds have history", - Nono pointed, - "Sounds carry with them the trace" of the context in which they were produced. The "evangelical" aspirations of the Darmstadt composers to pose themselves as "messiah" in establishing a new "new" from scratch, was a mere utopia. The comfortable sensation

⁴³ Henze, Hans Werner (1982) - Music and Politics: Collected Writings, 1953-1981. Translated by Peter Labanyi. Ithaca: Cornell University Press pp.155, p. 50.

of being, both, the means and the end in their compositions was a remedy for disaster where "anything goes". "Music will always remain a historical presence, a witness to those who consciously confront the historical movement", - was Nono's rightful conclusion. New structures should be born from a historic need and not from the composer's whim.⁴⁴

Noteworthy are the confessions by Edison Denisov, another avid participant of the Darmstadt School from the 1950s, a close friend of Nono, Boulez, and Xenakis'. There is not a single outdated technique; it is only the aesthetics that becomes outdated. No technique should be dismissed as "outdated" - as it can always turn out to be not only useful, but in fact, essential. If any technique ever dies, it happens all by itself - and not as a result of public obstruction. If you want to find your own way, before anything else you must master every technique that has existed before you - even those that are considered dead - for instance, strict polyphony or even earlier. Before you try out at least a couple of works in such a technique, it is impossible to tell whether you need it or not. Everything should be realized not theoretically, but through practice, "from inside".⁴⁵

These conclusions should be understood as the outcome of sustained investigation of the standing principles of avant-garde. When Denisov writes in his notebooks that more and more he withdraws from using serialism, that he sees series as a background device, unnecessary and even harmful for melodic content - where the series is likely to introduce unnaturalness and scholasticism - it is the outcome of his experience of following the rules of a non-communicative technique.⁴⁶

It was the clash between the grammatical forms and the artistic aspirations that led Denisov to conclude that most modernistic compositions elaborate on "dull and empty melodic intonations", and for many composers, intonation, as a category, does not exist at all. Microstructures have enlivened music but made its texture so fractured that it crumbles into micro-specs. Decorative dodecaphonic "dust" masks all the melody. And this is a great loss. There is a strong need in melodic line of long span capable of consolidating texture so that music form shapes out. One of the biggest defects of modernistic music is the ignorance of melodic intonation.⁴⁷

It is the break with tradition that Denisov blames for the degradation in the expressive capacity of new music. It must have been hard for him to step over his own venues back in the 1960s and 1970s, but he had courage to face the facts. He acknowledged that the innovativeness of the 1950s was artificial, a form of "shock therapy" as an attempt to bring the aging body of modernism back to life. And indeed after serialism was quickly exhausted and abandoned, the best representatives of avant-garde turned back to the national and European traditions. Denisov believed that "neo-romanticism" and minimalism are empty and "capitulatory" movements, not really "dangerous" to the progress of conceptual music - because they are "weak and accidental" - but very harmful for the tradition, since they both fake it with "pseudo-tradition".⁴⁸

⁴⁴ Nono, Luigi (1999) - Historical Presence in Music Today. Trans. Bryan R. Simms. In: Composers on modern musical culture: an anthology of readings on twentieth-century music, Schirmer Books, New York, p. 168-174.

⁴⁵ Composers on modern composition. Anthology. (2009) [Kompozitory o sovremennoi kompozitsii. Hrestomatiya] ed. Kiuregian T.S., Tzenova V.S., Moskovskaya Konservatoriya, Moscow p. 278.

⁴⁶ *ibid.* p. 279.

⁴⁷ *ibid.* p. 283.

⁴⁸ *ibid.* p. 284.

By the end of his career Denisov came to realize that the artificial grammars of new music were inferior to the traditional grammar and believed that any attempts to replace these artificial grammars with newer grammars, that are artificial in some other ways - are futile. The most effective way for a composer to write expressive music is by restoring the *modus operandi* of the modernistic era of the beginning of the 20th century: to skew the proportion of novelty and utilize the bulk of the traditional grammar as the base for some innovative treatment – and not to completely replace the old grammar with a new one.

Paradoxically though, end of serialistic dominance in the 1970s did not lead to the restoration of communicative techniques. Being realistic apparently is very hard for the modern conceptual composer. In 1993 Ligeti was still finding ties of post-modernistic technicality stiffening: "I am in a prison: one wall is the avant-garde, the other wall is the past, and I want to escape." He recalled how becoming an avant-garde artist felt like being accepted in a prestigious Pall Mall club with strict rules: "tonality out", melodies together with periodic rhythms, tabooed. Then, after Darmstadt was over, "everything is allowed", but "one cannot simply go back to tonality". There must be a way of "neither going back nor continuing the avant-garde".⁴⁹

Even more conflicting, is how a colleague of Denisov in the Moscow avant-garde group of the 1970s, Sofia Gubaidullina, sounds. She admits that she looks at the 18th and 19th century compositions "with envy". Their forms are so natural and effective that leaves a modern composer nothing but envy. Why cannot a modern composer utilize these forms if they are so good? Gubaidullina is set on her conclusion that "the resources of classical form are already exhausted", this is "a passed historic stage", and "we live in a different time".⁵⁰

But music grammar is not an oil field. How can it be exhausted? Idioms of music are very close to the idioms of speech in their function. When we speak, we do not discard a word because it dates back to the 16th century, and prefer another word, because it was introduced in the 20th century. In fact, any normal speaker ignores the words' date as long as the words suit his intention to express his idea and so long as it is understood by people. Even using an archaic word does not render the entire sentence archaic. Context has wonderful capacity to reconfigure the semantics of any single unit. And music is even more contextual than language.

It is possible to take historic musical idioms and configure them in a way to give rise to a coherent integrated form that does not sound anachronic. The impression of anachronism usually comes not from form but from content. As long as the older structures are mixed with the more modern ones, and as long as there is a timely and topical point to make, the work is not going to shock anyone as being unrelated to modern reality.

A testimony to this is Denisov's reconstruction of Schubert's unfinished *Lazarus*. Schubert's writing is cut right in the middle of an aria. It is very hard to pick the moment when Schubert's music finishes, and Denisov's music starts - although Denisov did not follow any sketches by Schubert. He simply made the music up - not even imitating Schubert's style. The idioms Denisov used include tonal progressions that can be found in the music of Richard Strauss and Mahler. But somehow there

⁴⁹ Ross, Alex (2008) - *The Rest Is Noise: Listening to the Twentieth Century*, Farrar, Straus and Giroux, New York, p. 506.

⁵⁰ Composers on modern composition. Anthology. (2009) [Kompozitory o sovremennoi kompozitsii. Hrestomatiya] ed. Kiuregian T.S., Tzenova V.S., Moskovskaya Konservatoriya, Moscow, p. 355.

is a strong sense of stylistic unity and coherence of structure, without any red flags popping out alarming “outdatedness”.⁵¹

Nikolai Korndorf is an example of a composer who was formed within the avant-garde music, but by the 1980s became dissatisfied with the stiffness of its techniques and tried out minimalism. After his Symphony No.3 (1989) he realized that it is the diatonic major and the metric repetitiveness of minimalism that are responsible for limiting the scope of his expression, very much like the serial and the aleatoric techniques. *Get out!* (1995) became his revolt against the boredom and emptiness of minimalism. In it, the musicians consistently act out attempts to relief themselves of the music’s repetition but become caught into an endless canon - until one after another they fall off, and the last of them tears the score apart.

Korndorf started looking for some fusion of styles capable of providing enough contrast to generate a dramatic content. As a musician, he was mostly influenced by his conducting teacher, Leo Ginzburg, an accomplished “vitalist” performer (according to Taruskin’s classification). The instinct to communicate to the audience was ingrained in Korndorf, himself a talented conductor (he won the All-Union competition in 1976), pushing him to expand into areas of old orthodox chant, historic styles of classical music, and histrionic action. Symphony No.4 “*Underground music*” (1996) reflected this new fusion: rock, Soviet mass songs, folk, bard song, gypsy romances, street drunk songs, chants, quotations from Haydn, Mozart, Beethoven, Mahler, Mussorgsky, Orff, and Shostakovich - not as a collage or parody, but as an integrative serious artwork.⁵²

Korndorf’s artistic development, most evident in his four symphonies, is characteristic of a contemporary composer who has something to say to the audiences: there is no other way to reach the listener but to speak conventional musical idioms. There is no way around it - the challenge of the art of composition is still there, where Shostakovich, Britten, and Sibelius left it - in wrapping the familiar idioms in a way to form a coherent whole, aesthetically appealing to the listener.

The Avant-garde Heritage in the 21st Century

It appears that the trend of competition to invent new music structures, launched by Stravinsky, merged with the trend of inventing non-communicative compositional techniques – all to bring to life a persistent pattern that constrains contemporary composers and makes it very difficult for them to explicitly express whatever they have to say – if anything at all.

There is a “modernistic syndrome” in place: the irrational belief that reusing an expression that someone used longer than a decade ago is necessarily bad and unacceptable - that music has to be put together according to some completely original principles, and that speaking in an intelligible way, up to a point, clearly and casually, debases art and is an encroachment on the “freedom of expression”.

⁵¹ Schubert-Denisov (1996) - Lazarus D689. Bach Collegium Stuttgart, Helmuth Rilling. Hanssler Classics CD p. 98-111.

⁵² Dubinec, Irina (2002) - Ya bezuslovno oshushayu sebia Russkim kompozitorom: Avtobiografiya s liricheskimi otstupleniyami [Being a Russian composer: An autobiography with lyrical retreats] Muzykal’naya Akademiya [Musical Academy] (2) p. 52-64.

They say that avant-garde is left so far behind that its remoteness does no longer allow a contemporary composer to sound “avant-garde” in strict meaning of this word. But in reality, this change did not transpire into the restoration of the centuries-old tradition of communicative classical music.

Today, composers like Korndorf are rare, whereas composers like Tristan Murail are all over - and Murail is quite conscious of the similarity of his compositional practices to those of the high avant-garde of the 1950s. He continues to search for innovative ideas and materials, both at a technical level as well as aesthetically, “to create new sonic/musical objects”. Murail admits in the fault of avant-garde in emptying the concert halls but thinks that cutting avant-garde off would be a wrong response: if only they could wait for a little longer - until the IRCAM composers would develop a better arsenal of tools for generating the “spectral music”!⁵³

Murail seriously believes that it is possible to build a new musical language based on the study of timbre at IRCAM, and to initiate “a coherent discourse” in this new language. He goes at length into technical discussions of what constitutes an “atom” and an “object” of this language and gives rather scarce considerations to the semantic aspect of this “would-be language”. He is somewhat more attentive than Stockhausen to the perceptibility of this new language. However, he appears to have a limited engagement with the principles of semiotics, believing that to the listener “a beautiful sound of cello, with nice vibrato” means just “a beautiful cello sound with vibrato”. He thinks that teaching the listener to “dissect the contents” of a sound into its spectral components - “all of which have their own lives” - would do the trick and turn the listener’s experience into discourse.

Murail equates the spectral analysis with semiosis: having the listener derive the subclasses of the object class ‘arpeggio’ in the manner similar to a computer program segmenting an audio stream - as a menu of possible operations, i.e. broken arpeggio: a unidirectional motion, or a zigzag path. He refers to Debussy as an example of such syntax that presumably stands beyond thematic development yet providing a “good set” of “anchor points” for the listener’s perception. Murail is excited about the possibility of bypassing thematic organization and formal models: “if we now add in the idea of process—transformation from one texture to another or generation of objects whose characteristics vary progressively—we obtain some absolutely fascinating results”.⁵⁴

Certainly, Murail’s compositions do sound interesting sonically. They carry a peculiar aesthetic quality and can be compared to instrumentation of Ravel or R. Strauss, which also can be appreciated as such, quite apart from the communicative content of their music - and the timbral coloration may enhance the communication. However, semiotically meaningless but pleasant and entertaining changes of timbral coloration in Murail's works are *not* of the same kind as the instrumentation of Ravel or R. Strauss. Early modernists still used timbres in conventional ways to convey a desired expression in support of the qualia of other expressive means (e.g., the timbre of flute to convey a beautiful yet dispassionate and distant image, or of oboe - to depict a pastoral scene or impart a melancholic character).

The only thing learned by Murail from avant-garde’s failure with the audiences is the importance of communication, which he understands in an extremely naïve way: as an intention to call the listener’s attention to certain auditory elements that are perceptible by the ear, and that can be

⁵³ Murail, Tristan (2005) - After-thoughts. Contemporary music review, 24(2-3) p. 269-272.

⁵⁴ Murail, Tristan (2005) - Villeneuve-lès-Avignon Conferences, Centre Acanthes, 9-11 and 13 July 1992 Contemporary Music Review, 2005, Vol. 24 Issue 2/3, p. 187-267.

logically united into a sequence of similar events. This is thought to satisfy the criterion of successful “conveying of a message” - the most that Murail could explain of how his new language is going to work - in all of his published papers.

Putting a checkmark next to such sketchy discussion, he is happy to jump to his favorite topic - chewing on the nitty-gritties of spectral structures. This is the same situation as with Stockhausen in relation to his favorite topic of “timing”, or Cage with his favorite “chance” music. The same obsession with making a new language out of previously unexplored materials - with disregard to the basics of communication.

First of all, Debussy is one of the most thorough thematic developers in Western music, on par with Beethoven. Digging virtually into any piece by Debussy will reveal his meticulous attention to the motif work and thematic content of each motif. It is arguable that thematic arrangement of the motifs constitutes the music form as a compositional method for Debussy - and not thinking in terms of periods and sentences. Just a brief look into his *Syrinx* shows two thematically contrasting motifs, with the first, primary in its thematic importance, receiving development in bars 4 and 5, giving rise to a new thematic material at the end of the sentence, in bars 6-8.

The image displays three staves of musical notation for Debussy's *Syrinx*. The first staff (bars 1-4) is in treble clef, three flats key signature, and 3/4 time. It begins with a dynamic marking of *mf* and features a melodic line with slurs. The second staff (bars 5-8) continues the melodic line, including a triplet of eighth notes and a dynamic marking of *p*. The third staff (bars 9-12) shows further development, including a triplet of eighth notes and a dynamic marking of *p*, with the word "Retenu" above the final notes.

5. Example: Debussy – *Syrinx*.

Debussy's method consists in defining one laconic, usually diatonic motif as a "nucleus" for the work (or its big section) and then inferring as many variants from it as possible, involving expansion and extrapolation, occasionally using secondary motifs for contrasting purposes. This economy of thought creates an impression of concision, strong logical coherence, and density of expression that make it easy to recognize Debussy's music upon first hearing. Debussy builds music form by montage of a small chunks of limited thematic material, avoiding recapitulations and preferring variability to it, often with new thematic material added in conclusion of the piece or a section.⁵⁵

⁵⁵ Denisov, Edison (1983) - Modern music and the problems of evolution of the composer's technique [Sovremennaya muzyka i problemy evolutsii kompozitorskoi tekhniki] Sovetskii Kompozitor, Moscow p. 90-111.

A bigger problem is that many Western scholars simply do not understand that devices of thematic elaboration carry their own proprietary expression – in addition to the expression of melody, harmony, rhythm, and meter. For instance, fragmentation of a musical phrase generally expresses commotion, agitation, doubt, or conflict of some kind - to various extent, depending on which material was fragmented and how pronounced this fragmentation is. Conversely, the opposite of fragmentation - conjunction - expresses relaxation, release of tension, a sense of growing magnitude, and completion.

It is precisely the deliberate expressive use of such devices as fragmentation and conjunction that distinguishes music of Beethoven and the Romantic composers from Haydn and Mozart. Beethoven discovered this new aspect of musical expression in the late works by C.P.E. Bach, who should be credited as its pioneer. Debussy's method of transforming a nucleus motif is also expressive per se. In fact, it is one of the reasons for the peculiar semantics of impressionism in music. Other "impressionistic" composers, like Ravel, Ibert, Schmitt, Caplet, Severac, Respighi, Turina, Mompou, Clarke, and early Kodaly sound "impressionistic" exactly because they employ this "montage method" of thematic elaboration. It makes the music sound vague and sort of "sfumato", slightly washed out, as though using a series of brushstrokes instead of a clearly defined, pencil-like, melodic line.

In fact, the birthmark of impressionism in music - the presentation of vivid *subjective* "impressions" of the *objective* reality in a detached and meditative manner, always remaining external and pleasurable to the observer/listener, and never emotionally stirring - owes itself to the expression of this method of thematic elaboration forged by Debussy. The ongoing chain of motivic transformation is rhetorically loose and unclear - in contrast to the clear-cut fragmentations and conjunctions of the 18-19th century composers - and invites a "metaphoric" mode of perception, where the listener has to decipher a hinted symbolic meaning that is intertwined with a certain "atmospheric" mood.

Indeed, Debussy's music is an excellent model for the original technique that stays within the framework of traditional grammar. The only problem is that the language proposed by Murail has nothing to do with Debussy. The primary source of meaning in music is convention. But convention applies to the structural elements that are already in use and are recognized by a significant number of music users as a particular entity, and are associated with a particular character, image, attitude, or action by virtue of symbolic similarity of the sound to the connoted semantic value. To users of all kinds of music, the puncture rhythmic figure is known as a musical entity and is associated with a bouncy mode of action and a brisk character, because jumping creates uneven pattern where the springing legs take longer to throw the body up than to when it lands. A brisk character is a property of someone engaged in such action. And the pattern of the "long-short" rhythm matches the pattern of a bouncy action. This is how listening to puncture rhythm becomes meaningful.

Listening to the spectral "swell" of a strange sounding sonance cannot be meaningful to the listener, simply for the absence of any convention related to such auditory object. Moreover, it is not a given that the listener will actually be able to register such swell as a discrete sonic unit. Stating that hearing a spectral arpeggio and then classifying it as a broken arpeggio constitutes "making meaning" is a indication of limited engagement with the fundamentals of semiotics. Meaning is a piece of information attached to a particular reproducible physical manifestation by the power of convention. Hearing that arpeggio is broken constitutes analysis, but not semiosis. Otherwise, where is the piece of information assigned to the virtue of being broken? This information ought to be physically unrelated to the body of the sign. "Brokenness" cannot be the "meaning" of arpeggio,

because it is a property of arpeggio. “Brokenness” of arpeggio can be a sign of damage by virtue of association between “breaking of something” that leads to its deterioration. However, for such connection to happen it is necessary for the sound of broken spectral arpeggio: 1) to sound in a detrimental way; 2) to be identifiable as a discrete auditory event; 3) to be supported by the convention amongst the members of the audience.

Murail omits any discussion of these three eminent conditions for his language to work. Instead of carefully reviewing the lexicon of his language, sign by sign, and aspect by aspect, he cheerfully declares that beautiful vibrato of cello should mean “beautiful vibrato of cello” to the listener, and proceeds to technicalities of how spectral data can be segmented. What this says is that Murail only wishes to communicate to the audience, but, in fact, he has nothing to say. All his ideas are concerned with what kind of material can be exposed to the listener, and nothing of what he says in his papers concerns the content he wishes to express.

Moreover, just like Stockhausen and other “high” avant-gardists, Murail either does not understand, or does not want to understand, that “sound” cannot be the content of “sound”. Form cannot be content - there is a reason why there are two words to express these two aspects, and not one - and “form” and “content” are not synonyms. Content is placed into form so that content would be readily available for the senses of the user. Form serves as the container for content - without the content, it is empty and meaningless.

Sound structures that do not possess content are no different than phonetic poems in pseudo-languages by Tristan Tzara. What they primarily convey is the author’s detachment from conventional expressive intent. These compositions may initially surprise and engage the audience, but without conventional communicative content, listener fatigue is likely to set in.

The only way to avoid such impression is to convince the audience that such reaction is “wrong”, and that there is some hidden value in listening to such sound structures that they fail to understand. In order to succeed in such suggestion, the author has to be supported by an entire institution of authorities. In the past, such support was provided by public institutions for ideological concerns. However, subsidization has severely damaged the entire state of affairs in serious Western music.

That is why now the consensus is that egalitarian policies should be stopped. It appears that Murail agrees with this, but only in words, whereas in his actions he still creates “avant-garde products” in the hope that some power player will take his work and push onto the consumer convincing him that that is what he needs.

Murail treads along the footprints of Stockhausen: the same obsession with the innovative technique, the same lack of interest in matters of perception and semiosis, the same pseudo-scientific imaging and association with modernity of technology (in this case, computer music and IRCAM research). Even the historic genealogy is there: “spectral music” is hooked to Debussy in search of authority, and a row of composers are reviewed in order to be dismissed for “inadequacy” of their approaches, from Schoenberg to Glass, and Adams, with Scelsi chosen as the prophet to claim the ultimate “trueness” of the new proposed timbral language - language without meaning, but the next “hot act”.⁵⁶

⁵⁶ Murail, Tristan (2005) - Scelsi and L'itinéraire: The Exploration of Sound. *Contemporary Music Review*, 2005, Vol. 24 Issue 2/3, p. 181-185.

The non-communicative model of musical language, formulated during the late 1940s, keeps reviving like Phoenix - with each progressive “ism” burning the previous one - all in order for the same organism to resurrect from the ashes. The principal difference from the legendary bird, though, is that the reborn organism comes out defective and lives for a few years rather than a half-millennium. Technically speaking, we should speak of “post-avant-garde” to refer to this cultural phenomenon that keeps functioning after the dismissal of serialism and aleatory - that are usually associated with “avant-garde”.

Are Most of Contemporary Composers Technically Underqualified?

A chain of techniques, each deposing the previous one for its most pronounced “sins” (rigidity of serialism, randomness of aleatory, redundancy of minimalism), like a domino effect, descends from Schoenberg’s dodecaphony. It is the presumption of musical immanence elevated by Schoenberg to the status of law of music form, that inspires rejection of any extraneous source of information including “meaning” per se.

The audience tends to be viewed as susceptible to the influence of popular music -- not as participants to be engaged, but as subjects to be guided. Popular music became the principal antagonist. Musical past “died” but was fine for public performance provided that modern works received their due.

All other forms of music were put in “quarantine”: Western folk, non-Western traditional, ethnic, and urban music, along with historic classical styles (which were OK to play but not to compose). They were all regarded as “impure” with various degrees of contamination by the “popular” virus. Subsequently, the lexicon of avant-garde and post-avant-garde was starved of conventional idioms, crippling the capacity of talented composers to convey what they had to say to the audiences.

Specifically, tonality and meter have been “quarantined” from times of Schoenberg’s life to the modern day. Whenever a restricted use of tonality or meter was allowed, as in minimalism, the resulting music was not organized along the lines of tonal or metric idioms, but in mere mimicry of them, maintaining the compositional framework of Schoenbergian autonomy. Incorporation of ethnic or historic models within the sterile formalistic framework, instead of fusing with ethnic or historic prototypes, only creates distance and transcends them.⁵⁷

That is why, no matter what “ism” inspired an author, the resultant work has remained historically and geographically aberrant from the world we live in and appears alien to the audiences. Paradoxically, just as drawing from jazz, folk, exotic non-Western music was inspiring the modernists of the beginning of the 20th century, the modernists of today feel awkward exposing authentic music in their works and prefer to deconstruct these exogenous models and reassemble them within the self-enclosed avant-garde framework. Such incorporations are often believed to be sufficient to revitalize the post-avant-garde idiom.⁵⁸

⁵⁷ Born, Georgina (2000) - Musical modernism, postmodernism, and others. In: Introduction to Western music and its others. Ed. G. Born and D. Hesmondhalgh, University of California Press, Berkeley and Los Angeles, p. 12-20.

⁵⁸ *ibid.*

Yet another paradox is that the early modernism puts popular music forms into use to shock the audiences with a low-brow agenda, provoke scandals, and earn points in social protest against the philistine culture. The post-minimalist composers, like Louis Andriessen, Frederic Rzewski, and their followers, embrace rock and jazz culture in an attempt to attract audiences, testifying to the fact that rock and jazz have higher status in the public eye than the avant-garde legacy. This in itself should be regarded as a proof of utmost failure and transgression of principles: from Adorno's and Schoenberg's repulsion of popular culture to begging the popular audience to patronize "serious music" - using the cultural authority of the high art institutions (universities, concert-halls) to sanctify that which appears to be profanity, according to their principles.⁵⁹

Engaging with popular idioms is often easier for the post-avant-garde composer than mastering traditional musical language. A significant part of this likely has to do with the decline of craftsmanship in modern composers. Sixty years of fasting would break any organism. Most of the modernists of the 1920s, including Schoenberg and Stravinsky, could produce music of "museum" quality. Their choice of idioms was completely voluntary.

The next generation was already compromised in quality: Schoenberg had his *Verklärte Nacht*, and Stravinsky - *Petrushka* and *The Firebird*, but composers like Boulez and Stockhausen could not afford to write in traditional idioms - that is why their mastery of harmony, melody, and form remained untested. Most Western composers born in the beginning of the 20th century received profound training in traditional techniques but abandoned them upon graduation. However, when they started teaching composition, their students inevitably obtained lower quality instruction in traditional techniques, since their teachers lacked first-hand experience in writing publicly successful works in traditional idioms.

There is a certain unfairness in why the composers are allowed to violate grammar, and performers are not. No performer would be acknowledged as professionally fit without being able to perform pieces from the technically advanced canonic repertoire. But modern composers get away with receiving the status of maestro, while many of them have not demonstrated the ability to compose a convincing song, sonata, quartet, or concerto using conventional canonic idioms. Many of these composers effectively conceal their limited grounding in traditional craft behind the framework of "unconventional" modern techniques.

In the Soviet bloc countries, the policies of socialist realism required all musical schools to implement traditional harmony, counterpoint, and music form, and teaching by the same standards that were employed before modernism. Denisov and Schnittke were trained by their teachers (respectively, Shebalin and Golubev, both accomplished masters of tonal idioms) to fluently express themselves in traditional forms, and to which their earlier works can attest.

However, many of their Western contemporaries simply do not have works written in traditional tonal idioms held to the artistic standards of the past - i.e. Xenakis and Boulez. Progressive increase in presence of avant-garde philosophy in the Western academia relaxed the emphasis on traditional disciplines of music, making them look like vestiges of unrelated past, and produced composers, incapable of writing a good quality tonal quartet, fugue, or symphony.

⁵⁹ Fink, Robert (1998) - *Elvis Everywhere: Musicology and Popular Music Studies at the Twilight of the Canon*, American Music, Vol. 16, No. 2 (Summer, 1998), pp. 135-179.

A great number of modern composers have no other choice but to pursue the phantom - the “phantasy that one could invent a new musical language without reference to other musics, without recourse to syncretism, stripped of representational intent, and through a process of pure conceptual invention”.⁶⁰

It is easier for a post-modernistic composer to look for some magical way of discovering a phenomenon that was overlooked by previous composers, and to derive from it a new "universal fix" - like Stockhausen's "unified time" that could be "spectral music", with its idea of inference of music form from timbre. Or, Pyotr Meshchaninov's mathematical theory of musical evolution, for which Gubaidulina has high hopes to provide a modern composer with a “reliable”, authorized by science, modernized analog of dodecaphony - a “correct” way of putting sounds together.⁶¹

Brought to life by the emancipation movement, in the form of emancipation of dissonance, it is “the modernistic syndrome” that itself calls for emancipation - to save modernistic composers from modernism in order to let them be really free in communicating to their audiences!

The isolationist obsession of post-war avant-garde with quasi-scientific ontology and false confidence in self-sufficiency, eventually led to the demise of Darmstadt school, with its champions (such as Luigi Nono and Franco Evangelisti) denouncing their creation, seeing it as a dictatorial attempt of forceful takeover in new music (a “dodecaphonic police”), and other participants dissolving their membership due to the differences in their musical orientation. However, the precedence of non-communicative technique was already established – the damage was done.

The algorithm of “inventing” a principle, justifying it historically, elaborating it into a technique, fabricating a sort of “fiction” to accommodate the dry matters of its technicalities, and making an “evangelical” claim about it - a formula for launching a “new thing” is still very much alive. After all, Stockhausen, Boulez, and Cage have proven their “branding” scheme to be quite effective in building their name recognition.

The legacy of “innovation” in sake of “innovation”, in perfect vacuum, free from any “contamination” by the audience, keeps inducing confusion amongst composers, no matter how they stand in relation to Stockhausen, Boulez, or Cage. Thus, Cornelius Cardew who initially served as an assistant to Stockhausen and composed total serialist music. After exposure to the music by Cage, he dropped serialism and switched to improvisation in free jazz manner with a newly founded group AMM (1965), in what they called “laminal” style, characterized by long tones and rests. In parallel, he created his opus magnum, *Treatise* (1963–67), the world biggest (193 pages) graphic score of invented notation, without any instructions as to how to decipher the graphic elements in it. Cardew left it completely up to the performers, following what he perceived as the thesis of Ludwig Wittgenstein’s *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus*: “people set up rules for pleasure, and then hold by them.”⁶²

⁶⁰ Born, Georgina (2000) - Musical modernism, postmodernism, and others. In: Introduction to Western music and its others. Ed. G. Born and D. Hesmondhalgh, University of California Press, Berkeley and Los Angeles, p. 17.

⁶¹ Composers on modern composition. Anthology. (2009) [Kompozitory o sovremennoi kompozitsii. Hrestomatiya] ed. Kiuregian T.S., Tzenova V.S., Moskovskaya Konservatoriya, Moscow, p. 353.

⁶² Anderson, Virginia (2006) - Well, It's a Vertebrate ...”: Performer Choice in Cardew's *Treatise*. Journal of Musicological Research, Volume 25, Numbers 3-4, -4/July-December 2006, pp. 291-317.

By taking existing elements of notation, distorting them and mixing them up with geometric symbols and elements of technical drawings, Cardew strove to illustrate Wittgenstein's propositions to investigate "the structure of what can be said" by "plotting the limits".⁶³ Influenced by David Tudor's ideas of giving performers more creative rights, Cardew decided to enable each performer of his *Treatise* to "give of his own music—he will give it as his response to my music, which is the score itself".⁶⁴ This concept was created in polemics to Stockhausen's attempts to engage aleatory in his *Plus-Minus* (1963), which caused a sarcastic reaction in Cardew. It seems that being caught into the heat of competitive discussion about the "form-schemes" and their impact on the performers, Cardew was not aware of the fact that his *Treatise* was not really a composition, since it lacked a preconceived scheme of organization of sounds that would direct the listening experiences of the audience.

6. Example: Cornelius Cardew – *Treatise* (fragment).

In fact, *Treatise* consists of pages filled with graphic signs that bear no prescribed connection to whatever the musicians decide to play. By analogy, musicians could derive performance ideas from examining cracks on the walls -- but that would hardly constitute a musical composition.

The utmost instability of the avant-garde composer's axiology is striking in case of Cardew. In the early 1970s, he suddenly veered toward Maoism, denounced his *Treatise* altogether with improvisatory music, and published the book "*Stockhausen Serves Imperialism*", where in Maoist repentant confessional style, he acknowledged his sins and condemned the Western avant-garde. He swore in loyalty to the new task of "integrating with the working-class movement as a whole", and a group of working musicians, in particular, with the purpose to create simple music for simple people [apparently, such as his rather awkward piano miniature "*Long Live Chairman Mao!*" (1973),

⁶³ *ibid.*

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

arranged as a cross between a march and a retro popular song on the theme unmistakably resembling “*Raindrops Keep Fallin' on My Head*” (1969) by David and Bacharach.⁶⁵

7. Example: Cardew – Long Live Chairman Mao!

Volatility of axiological views is as characteristic to the “modernistic syndrome” as negativity in attitude, attraction to scientifically sounding postulates, and eagerness for innovation. Consequently, the grammatical organization in music of the avant-garde and post-avant-garde, displays volatile traits of the tendency to hybridize various techniques. At the absence of an audience-based convention, fusion of unrelated techniques is likely to induce fluctuations in the principles of organization, both, within a work and between few works of the same composer. An example of such grammatical instability can be found in almost all major works by Alfred Schnittke – either in the form of “idealistic” citations of famous old “tonal” composers or “sarcastic” reproductions of various styles of popular music.⁶⁶

It is as though contemporary composers, hit by the avant-garde conditioning, instinctively try to reconnect with “traditional idioms” from the good old past – only to find that their compositional reflexes resist this “healthy air” return to conventional grammar, as though conditioned by long habituation. From the perspective of the mastery of compositional techniques, this inability to generate a new organic blend of the traditional “old” and the idiosyncratic “new” boils down to the mere lack of compositional skills: after all, master-composers of the past as a rule faced the same problem of bridging the “old” and “new” forms of expression, but unlike our contemporary composers, were able to achieve an aesthetically convincing merger.

When “Non-communicative” Music is Misinterpreted as “Communicative”

The biggest obstacle in studying “serious music” of post-1940s is the confusion of non-communicative and communicative devices. Even within the grammatical system that is non-communicative, individual works can be meaningful through genre or style referents, collage, quotations, associations of timbre of an instrument with a particular type of music, etc. Also, even when strictly following the techniques of total serialism or aleatory, there were notable composers who proved to be an exception who managed to communicate specific images or characters through their music - like Ligeti, Nono, Berio, Maderna, Lutoslawski, and Penderecki. They defied the limitations of the technique they chose to adhere to.

⁶⁵ Cardew, Cornelius (1974) - Stockhausen Serves Imperialism. Latimer New Dimensions Limited, London, p. 6-8.

⁶⁶ Ivashkin, Alexandr. *Alfred Schnittke (20th Century Composers)*. New York, NY: Phaidon Press, 1996.

However, their success does not add any credit to the grammatical system they used. Total serialism, aleatory, timbral music, and minimalism are all varieties of styles/techniques that are all based on non-communicative grammars. This means that if a composer follows the prescribed techniques of composing such music, the result will be an abstract progression of meaningless music structures. Meaningful communication can occur only if extra-systemic, non-grammatical factors are brought into music.

Some techniques, like dodecaphony, present a mixed case: thus most works by Schoenberg and Berg are communicative and idiomatic, whereas works by late Webern and Krenek are not. Objectively speaking, dodecaphony as a grammatical system severely limits musical communication as compared to the traditional tonal system. However, it does not exclude expression. Similar semiotic restrictions characterize other 20th century grammars: Stravinsky's or Bartok's. In general, all post-tonal techniques that avoid traditional metric organization tend to narrow the content that is to be transmitted.

On the other hand, they make expression of a particular kind of content more vivid and more detailed than the traditional tonal grammar. Thus, for Stravinsky, his expression of mystic cruelty in "The Rite of Spring" or the primitive crude expressions that entertain the crowd in his "Petrouchka" cannot be reproduced by conventional harmony and metric organization. I have heard many compositions by other composers trying to achieve this effect, but not as well as Stravinsky. On the other hand, Stravinsky never had success expressing collective jubilee and festivity (like Beethoven's Ode to Joy) or deep yet sweet melancholy (like Tchaikovsky's "October") by means of his unconventional techniques.

Yet an additional problem in the 20th century research is that so many composers after the 2nd World War shifted from one technique to another on the spur of the moment - as new compositional techniques became available. Hybridization of techniques makes the task of semiotic analysis for these works very difficult.

There are cases where it is extremely hard to draw the line as to whether the composition is communicative or not. An example of this is late Stravinsky's experiments with serialism. When Kara Karayev (aka, Gara Abulfaz oghlu Garayev) met Stravinsky in Los Angeles, during the first International Music Festival held at UCLA, he asked Stravinsky if while composing whether he internally heard the sounds of his serial music. Stravinsky answered that it was impossible for him to hear it all. But then, he remarked: "he often was pleasantly surprised while listening to his works performed later."⁶⁷

It looks like this case qualifies as genuinely "experimental", where at least certain aspects of composition are not idiomatically cognized by the composer, contributing to the "game of chance" phenomenon - reserving space for "surprise". Such model would definitely not hold in relation to idiomatic text: picking words by some computer algorithm and sticking them in a sentence is not going to produce an aesthetically valid or meaningful poem. However, with Stravinsky, the situation is not that "clear cut" - he has earned the reputation of being a diligent tester of his compositions, paying enormous attention to the aggregate sound generated in his works in particular places.

It is possible that Stravinsky controlled his choice of the serialistic rhythms to a big extent without being aware of it. Such situations require extra investigation on the part of researchers. However, it

⁶⁷ Soviet Music Magazine report, ISSN 0038-5085 [Sovetskaya Muzyka] 1961 No.9 p.121.

appears quite conclusive that after the 2nd World War the practice of heavily relying on compositional techniques became so widespread that many composers did not see anything wrong in writing “from head” rather than “by ear”.

It is extremely important for a musician to distinguish between non-communicative and communicative breeds of music. It would be futile to labor over interpretation of Cage’s or Stockhausen’s compositions, when pretty much anything goes - in complete accordance with their intention, as long as there is some minimal resemblance with the notation. However, performing a composition by Lutoslawski or Ligeti would require serious investigation into the compositional technique, its history, its limitations, and the composer’s identity. Performance of modern repertoire imposes extensive musicological component in preparing for performance and requires critical judgment and artistic intuition.

In the end, it is left to the performer to judge whether or not the post-modernistic compositional technique is worth learning. After all, the linguistic model here holds pretty well: what is the payback for learning a particular language. Learning the technique of fugue allows to communicate the ideas common to Baroque culture. Learning the dodecaphonic technique opens the world of Expressionistic aesthetics. The question for a post-modernistic technique is then: what kind of expression it enables and how rewarding is its communication?

The negative answer to this question is the reason why some of the finest performers, legendary for their expressiveness, avoided playing post-modernistic music during the peak of its reign. Heifetz made a note that when he occasionally played works by contemporary composers, it was to “discourage the composer from writing any more” and to remind himself about the greatness of Beethoven. Piatigorsky was somewhat curious about “new music”, and occasionally even commissioned some, but referred to these compositions as “dead-born babies”.

Since the very profession of a performer depends on his success to communicate, performers often find themselves in a position where they struggle to find expression in something that does not have any, by design. A good example of this is the creative output of Stravinsky, whose denial of any emotional content in music became well known (“music is, by its very nature, essentially powerless to express anything at all”).⁶⁸

Yet many performers during the 1920-1930s performed his works emotionally, along the lines of Romantic model of performance, as evident from their recording that they left behind. A good example is Samuel Dushkin, the pupil of Auer and Kreisler - quite passionately sounding artist, as expected from a world class violinist in the first half of the 20th century. Stravinsky never, ever expressed any dissatisfaction in Dushkin’s exceedingly emotional rendition of his works. Quite in contrary, he praised Dushkin for his refined taste, great musical culture, and exceptional professionalism.⁶⁹

So, on one hand, Stravinsky makes statements to the effect that the ideal performer is a church toller, and the ideal conductor is a military band tact-beater - because they just do their job accurately and nothing more. Yet, on another hand, he demands exquisite phrasing, dynamic nuances, and expects the performers to figure them out from grasping the spirit of the work. Never

⁶⁸ Stravinsky, Igor (1936) - *Stravinsky: An Autobiography*, Simon & Shuster, New York, p. 83

⁶⁹ Stravinsky Igor (2005) - *Hronika moyei muzykal’noi zhizni [Chroniques de ma vie]* ed. & comment. by I. Vershinina, Kompozitor, Moscow, p. 355-6.

in his copious publication did Stravinsky name a single performer who had “over-interpreted” his music, although many of them in their recordings applied the “vitalist” treatment [ex. Fournier].

According to Soulima Stravinsky, his father criticized those performers who "only played notes" and "did not know what to do with those notes", insisting that "performers have to be intelligent". Soulima testifies that when his father performed, he was seeking to put into sound a lot more than was printed in the score; his manner was not dry and alienated as many would think (ibid p. 396-7).

Numerous of Stravinsky’s recordings [over a dozen hours in total] only add to the confusion. In his autobiography he stated that, having been disappointed by constant misunderstanding of performers of his compositions, he took great labor upon himself to leave reliable performance references for his most important works. Each of such recordings involved a great deal of thought and elaboration, and the result should be regarded as a model for any future performance. He specified that faithful reproduction of his model was all he would consider great from any conductor.⁷⁰

Unfortunately, Stravinsky’s multiple versions of the same work (e.g., five versions of *The Rite of Spring* on record) do not agree with each other. He regretted that the conductors’ pride prevented them from listening to his recordings prior to rehearsals with the orchestra.⁷¹ It looks like he himself had too much dignity to double-check his previous records.

Moreover, there is reason to doubt the integrity of Stravinsky’s directions. If his complaints of the liberties that “vitalist” conductors such as Pierre Monteaux took by routinely crossing out the composer’s metronome markings, and writing in his own, and executing unwritten tempo modification, and Romanticizing the style, then it is logical to expect a perfect “geometrical” performance from Stravinsky himself. Monteaux’s 1929 recording featured speeding up the *Danse sacrale* from the original M=126 to 148-156; major slowing down in the middle; and two gradual tempo changes designed to provide the melodic line with a Wagnerian style rubato – all of which were in clear violation of the “geometrical” prescription by Stravinsky.

In fact, Stravinsky edited out all tempo fluctuations from this dance in the 1929 edition, and in 1938 specifically instructed Alfredo Molinari to keep the dance strictly at 126. This is the tempo that he himself recorded in 1960. However, in 1969 he insisted that Robert Craft make accelerando towards the end of *Danse sacrale*. And his 1921 Pleyela piano roll exhibits not only accelerando, but the tempo at M=148, and a dramatic slowdown in the middle.⁷²

Apparently, Stravinsky either had double standards or had difficulties making up his mind. Whatever the reason, unfortunately, he created a common problem for the performer of the ultra-modernistic music, where the composer risks getting caught between various innovations. The performer is left the dilemma of either following what the composer preached or practiced.

The best compromise in such situation would be to investigate the score, identify the idiomatic units in it, and come up with a rendition by weighing what is known about the idioms in the score as well as the composer’s statements about his style. This makes the task of formulating the actual idioms of the 20th century music – as to how they sound rather than what is claimed by the composer – the most important requirement for the performance of modern music.

⁷⁰ Stravinsky, Igor (1936) - *Stravinsky: an autobiography*, Simon & Shuster, New York, p. 236-237.

⁷¹ ibid p. 236.

⁷² Fink, Robert (1999) - "Rigorous (M = 126)": "The Rite of Spring" and the Forging of a Modernist Performing Style, *Journal of the American Musicological Society*, Vol. 52, No. 2, pp. 299-362.

Unfortunately, due to their esoteric organization, non-communicative post-modernistic works do not leave such opportunity – as they are very much like a book filled with strange combinations of letters in an unknown made-up language. Neither looking at such letters nor listening to their presumable sound gives any clue as to what such book is about.

Stravinsky's music is not like that. His scores reflect not pre-conceived rules of his own grammar, but the development of thematic material - very much like composers of the previous centuries. Before his serial period, Stravinsky was known to have composed "by ear" and to have thoroughly check every sonance on the piano before fixing it in the score, listening to it a number of times, and trying it again and again before writing it in the score, which is why his brothers used to call him "the piano tuner".⁷³

Stravinsky did not avoid the historic idioms of musical expression. In fact, he was very proud of his heritage. In his radio addresses before his performances he presented himself as "a direct heir" of Glinka and Tchaikovsky.⁷⁴ In the statements he made, what Stravinsky meant is that if a performer understood Tchaikovsky's music, he was then able to understand Stravinsky's music. Stravinsky (before 1936, when he had made his statement about his lineage) composed following the principles similar to Tchaikovsky, using similar idioms. That was why Heifetz and Piatigorsky performed the early Stravinsky.

The non-communicative techniques leave a performer with the choice either to fabricate the expressive content in music out of thin air in order to generate something appealing to the listener, or just to play notes, ignoring the audience altogether - as Stockhausen and Cage did - and hope (or not) for some "magical" result. In sake of accuracy, it should be noted that the seeds for such attitude are found in Stravinsky's rhetoric about the presumable unemotionality of music, and the shortsightedness of the public. Combined, such views conveyed the idea that it is unnecessary for the composer to be concerned about "being understood" and being bother with any conventions - supposedly, the critics and the audiences would find meaning in anything dumped at them – and that success is all the matter of purely gravitas on the part of the composer.

By the 1930s such view was firmly established amongst musicians and in the academia. Indeed, there are strong physiological grounds for the "wishful thinking" bias. Human need in emotional input is so strong and biologically ingrained that it does not take long for the public consensus to assign some emotional value to a musical composition after it is performed. This tendency is most pronounced in the traditional "communicative" music of the past. One of the most famous examples is the story of how Beethoven's *Piano Sonata No. 14* turned into the "*Moonlight*." Music history is full of such examples. As Melvin Rigg puts it: "if the composer leaves no interpretation of his production, it is usually not long before one is invented".⁷⁵

⁷³ Craft, Robert (1994) - *Stravinsky: Chronicle of a Friendship*, Vanderbilt University Press, Nashville, Tennessee, p. 138.

⁷⁴ Druskin M.S. (2009) - *The Collected Works*, vol. 4 Igor Stravinsky [Sobraniye proizvedenii, tom 4, I.S.] Kompozitor - Sankt-Petersburg, p. 490.

⁷⁵ Juslin, Patrik N.; Lindström, Erik (2010) - Musical expression of emotions: Modeling listeners' judgments of composed and performed features. *Music Analysis*, March 2010, Vol. 29 Issue: Number 3 p. 334-364.

The Performers' and Musicologists' Conundrum: to Make Sense of Senseless Music or not?

In relation to the temporal organization, paradoxically, despite the composers' aspirations for ultimate complexity, the ultra-modern techniques demonstrate a pronounced tendency for simplification. To begin with, the most intricate timing idea still depends on the perception of the performers who are conceiving it, then, on the performer's physiological ability to convert the prescribed timing into sounds - and finally, on the ability of the listeners to perceive such timing.

At the starting point of this scheme, the organization can be excruciatingly complex - like Stockhausen's *Himmelfahrt* (2005) for organ or synthesizer, soprano, and tenor. The composition is built on the chromatic scale of 24 different tempos - where the metronomic value for each tempo is derived from the preceding one by using a mathematical formula. These tempos correspond to the scale of 24 timbres - where complex timbres correspond to slower tempos. The keyboardist is required to perform in two different tempos simultaneously, with occasional addition of the vocal parts, stimulating the listeners as though to transcend from physical world to something "unimaginable—unheard—invisible".⁷⁶

The reality of performance renders all intentions of such music delusional. If Stockhausen's intention was to collide two streams of movement of specific proportion to suggest a particular auditory illusion, then his work already defeats his original concept: no human brain is capable of processing two tempos simultaneously; and even if it was possible by some miracle, no brain would allow to control the motor function in two different scales - and this is without consideration of keeping a particular fractional temporal ratio between two processes.

The performer is going to flatten all the notes into one stream, quantizing all the durations to the standard binary divisions, and most likely, make plenty of mistakes - which will pass completely unnoticed by the audience (and most likely, by the composer himself) who would perceive the music as an irrational progression of sounds contrasting in their timbre.

Will that transcend the audience into another world is a separate question, but the stream of data that they will process is equivalent to a single row of chaotic, haphazard digits - a task nearly impossible for sensation and comprehension, therefore bringing the auditory senses into the mode of an idle senseless "background" listening (mindlessly scrolling through the sounds).

By no means does such listening task impose any effort on the part of the listener. The truth of the matter is that such listening doesn't require any effort whatsoever!

Compare this to the task of following the music by early Stravinsky: *Pribaoutki*.

⁷⁶ Stockhausen, Karlheinz (2006) - Stockhausen-Courses Kuerten 2006: Composition Course on Klang, the 24 Hours of the Day: First Hour: Ascension for Organ or Synthesizer, Soprano and Tenor, 2004/05, Work No. 81. Kürten: Stockhausen-Verlag.

Moderato. ♩ = 92

Canto.
 Ну - тко, дя - дюш-ка Кор - ни-(и-и)-ло, За-(а-а)-пря - гай - - ко ты ко -
Con - so - le toi, vieil oncle Ar - mand; tu - t'fais bien trop de mau - vais

Piano.

8. Example: Stravinsky – *Pribaoutki*, No.1.

Constant metric alternations are combined with quite diverse rhythmic figures, including syncopation and ostinato figures. To this should be added hypermetric pulsations due to the periodically occurring pedal tones. Each phrase requires expressive timing, so does the vocal part in relation to the accompaniment. Ten bars of this music contain more information for the listener to process than an entire work by Stockhausen.

Non-communicative post-modernistic techniques put considerable pressure on musicology. There is infinite variety of grammars that can be invented in the absence of any pragmatic factors. There are already hundreds of methods of organizing musical structures created in the past 50 years, many of which are completely scholastic and abstract, devoid of any expressive capacity. Does the mere fact that a non-communicative grammar has been generated justify its scholarly study?

This is a serious question that needs an urgent answer. Specialists of the atonal music theory have collected a list of almost a hundred compositional techniques of the modern times. Many of them present a puzzle as to how to categorize them, to which of the multiple categories give priority, and how to distinguish between the composer's intentions and the way in which the music actually sounds, etc.⁷⁷

The textbooks on compositional techniques already look like an entry on “animals” in an ancient Chinese dictionary *“The Celestial Emporium of Benevolent Knowledge”* with the following categorization: (a) those belonging to the Emperor, (b) those that are embalmed, (c) those that are tame, (d) pigs, (e) sirens, (f) imaginary animals, (g) wild dogs, (h) those included in this classification, (i) those that are crazy-acting (j), those that are uncountable (k) those painted with the finest brush made of camel hair, (l) miscellaneous, (m) those which have just broken a vase, and (n) those which, from a distance, look like flies.⁷⁸

⁷⁷ Tzenova V.S. (2003) - Structural phenomenon of New music: compositional techniques [Strukturnyi fenomen Novoi muzyki: tehniki kompozitsii]. In: Sator tenet opera rotas; Y.N.Kholopov and his school. Moscow Tchaikovsky Conservatory, Moscow p. 275-282.

⁷⁸ Borges, Jorge Luis (1975) - Other Inquisitions: 1937-1952, University of Texas Press p. 101-105.

There is great need for setting certain criteria for investigation of compositional techniques. And the issues of communication, perception, and response to music should all be part of considering a technique as valid or “experimental”.

Post-modernistic composers who create non-communicative techniques love the word “experimental”. Thus, Cage dissuades those composers who find this term too disciplinary and obliges them to adhere to some order. He finds the word “apt” for the kind of music that calls for a gazing attitude towards an environment filled with things to look at, as if “one is a tourist” - provided the word “experimental” is understood “not as descriptive of an act to be later judged in terms of success and failure”.⁷⁹

But this is exactly what the term “experiment” denotes: a trial and error procedure carried out with the goal to verify a hypothesis. The logic follows naturally. If a composer takes advantages of calling his work “experimental” in order to avoid compliance to already accepted rules and laws, then he has to bear the consequences and prove the validity of new rules and laws.

An experiment leads either to its confirmation or dismissal. No science keeps a book of absolutely all experiments. Only the positive results of experiments are retained as theories. The experiments that do not turn out to be useful are discarded. It is about time for musicology to follow the same pursuit and audit the bulged corpus of experimental techniques. It would be productive to determine which techniques are qualified as a new functional form of music. Scholarly attention could focus on those techniques, rather than on experiments that have not yielded communicative results.

⁷⁹ Cage, John (1961) - *Silence: Lectures and Writings*, Wesleyan University Press, Hanover NH p. 13.